

ZURO

1975

*The Magazine of the History Society
Umtali Boys' High School*

ZURO 1975.

No. 8.

Editorial	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	2
Chairman's Report	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	3
Treasurer's Report	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	4
List of Membership	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	4
The History Society Committee	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	4
Minutes of Meetings:									
Mr. N.A.Hunt	-	Tribal Custom and Organisation	..	..	..	..	..	..	5
Mr. G.E.Harris	-	Experiences in a P.O.W.Camp	..	..	..	..	..	..	6
Mrs. M.Izzett	-	The Hunyani Survey	..	..	..	..	..	..	9
Mr. A.Hitschman	-	The S.I.B. and the Investigation of War Crimes	..	..	..	..	..	..	9
Trees of Historical Interest in Manicaland	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	13
The Move to New Untali		J.Harris	..	..	..	..	..	..	16
Mesopotamia : The Cradle of Civilisation		R.Papini	..	..	..	..	..	..	18
The Philosophy of History		S.Gilmour	..	..	..	..	..	..	21
Voltaire, The Founder of the Age of Reason		D.Warwick	..	..	..	..	..	..	26
Otto Skorzeny		P.Zorn	..	..	..	..	..	..	27
Manfred von Richthofen - The Red Baron		D.Wylie	..	..	..	..	..	..	29
Georges Boulanger		G.Grispos	..	..	..	..	..	..	38
The Atomic Bombing of Japan		M.Morkel	..	..	..	..	..	..	39
Illustrations:									
von Richthofen's Fighters	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	31
and His Victims	...	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	33
Map									
To Illustrate the Three Sites of Untali	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	20
History Society Crossword	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	44

oooOooo

EDITORIAL.

One point that was made obvious at the recent Sixth Form History Conference in Salisbury is that our syllabuses at school are very limited in their scope. Our degree of specialisation is, of course, very necessary for the passing of examinations, but history is a subject which must be studied in width as well as in depth if it is to be appreciated and fully understood. It is all very well learning facts about specific people and events but this makes history merely a scholastic exercise instead of what it should be : a study of why, and not merely how, man is where he is today. Every subject taught at school must be relevant and prepare the scholar in some way for later life, a task which classroom history alone does not adequately fulfill.

The purpose of 'Zuro' is to record the activities of the History Society (which unfortunately had to be curtailed somewhat this year because of various difficulties) and also to fill some of the many gaps in our historical knowledge. What you will read here is history as it should be - a tremendous variety of subjects apparently unconnected but all part of our study of man. The Rhodesiana Society recently reviewed 'Zuro 1974' and commented that "This is an outstanding publication and the wide interest and authenticity of the material would do credit to a professional learned journal. The Society must be one of boundless enthusiasm."

Much of the credit for this magazine must go to Mr. Barnes who, besides being President of the Society, has given us valuable assistance in every stage of publication. Our position as the largest society in the school, as the only society to publish articles and present its material to the public, and indeed as the only school society of its nature in the country, is largely due to the enthusiasm and energy which he devotes to history both in and outside the classroom.

'Zuro' is not published for us to teach you; you, the reader, must learn from it yourself.

S. Gilnour.

It is my pleasure as Chairman of the Society for 1975 to report a most successful year both in terms of attendance at meetings and active participation in society activities; this enthusiasm is perhaps best demonstrated by the continued increase in paid-up membership.

Throughout the year a number of speakers have addressed the Society on a variety of topics which were always well supported. Mr. Hunt, a retired Under-Secretary of Internal Affairs, spoke on the African Tribal System; Mr. Harris related his experiences in a P.O.W. camp in Germany; Mrs Izzett, President of the Prehistory Society of Rhodesia, and Miss Summers spoke on the findings of the Hunyani Survey; Mr. Hitschman told of his experiences in Fascist Italy and in investigating war crimes; Mr. Bekker, a previous Chairman of the Society, spoke on protected villages (keeps) in the north-eastern border regions.

Regrettably two expeditions had to be cancelled at the last moment owing to forces beyond our control. The first was to the Tanda Purchase Area to observe and record some recently discovered ancient ruins which had to be cancelled because of A.N.C. activity in the area; the second trip was to Mapungubwe and Baines' Drift (1975 is the centenary of Baines's death) in the north-western Transvaal. This was to have been in conjunction with the Rhodesiana Society but they had to cancel their plans at the last moment and we were compelled to follow suit. It is hoped that both trips will be completed next year, as will one to the Sabi-Lundi confluence to search for further evidence of Arab mooring sites.

In the first term the Society showed the film 'Waterloo' which was well attended and helped to boost appreciably the Society's funds.

Some useful work was done by a select committee on a tree project. Acting in unison with the Tree Society of Rhodesia a small group was assigned the task of gathering information on trees of historical significance in the area. A letter of appreciation has since been received from the Tree Society for a good job well done and the final result was published in the 'Umtali Post.'

I would like to convey our thanks to the Pioneers' and Early Settlers' Society for inviting twelve of our members on a day's outing up the Vumba to visit the Altar site, Leopard Rock and the house of Miss. Cripps.

My thanks as Chairman must go to Iain Gwyther for his efficiency as secretary, to Ralph Allen for keeping our funds in order, to Deidre Hunt for keeping the female element of the Society in control, to Rob Flowes for his work as research co-ordinator and curator of the museum, and to Steve Gilmour for his compilation of Zuro. My final thanks on behalf of the Society but particularly of the committee must go to Mr. Barnes, our President, for the considerable time he has devoted to the Society and for his unending encouragement and guidance offered at all times.

It is my confirmed belief that the enthusiasm of the Society will continue as in the past. We are proud of the fact that our society is both the most active and the best supported in the school. Finally I would like to take this opportunity on behalf of those leaving to wish the Society every success in 1976.

.....

TREASURER'S REPORT.

R.Allen.

<u>Credit.</u>		<u>Debit.</u>	
Subscriptions	£ 30.50	Film expenditure	£ 23.10
Film takings, Waterloo	45.63	O Level History prize	4.20
Donation, Mrs. Izzett.	2.00	Est. expenditure Zuro 1975.	60.00
" Mr. Ford.	2.50		
Est. income of Zuro, 1975.	25.00		
	<u>105.63</u>		<u>87.30</u>

Excess income over expenditure : £18.33

Once again our income exceeds expenditure, an indication of the profitability of keeping the annual History Society film.

There are sixty one paid-up members out of a total of ninety who have attended two or more meetings. It is of interest to note that this is the highest paid-up membership since 1970.

I am grateful to Deidre Hunt for increasing our membership from U.G.H.S., and to Mrs. Izzett and Mr. Ford, our two honorary members, for their interest in the Society and their generous donations to our funds.

.....

Membership.

R.Allen	S.Johnston	J.Olsen	B.Fleshman
G.Arthur	S.Kavalieratos	C.Orner	D.Hunt
H.Ball	F.Lombard	D.Orner	L.Jannaway
D.Bentley	L.Marais	R.Plowes	L.Kloppers
M.C.Bowler	P.Markham	S.Rault	S.Lamb
M.P.Bowler	M.Mason	S.Rigby	J.May
J.Carroll	C.Messenger	V.Sher	E.Mills
T.Carroll	P.Moore	D.Thomas	L.Mungle
T.Catsicas	M.Morkel	S.Thomas	M.Peart
P.Coventry	C.Munch	D.Williams	D.Ricco
R.de Zoeten	P.Murphy	V.Witt	D.Roberts
R.Forrester	B.Ness	P.Zorn	C.van der Riet
G.Grispos	P.Nicholas	<u>U.G.H.S.</u>	C.Walk
A.Gunn	T.Nolan	L.Ade	F.West
I.Gwyther	K.Northern	F.Campbell	
G.Holcroft	D.Ogilvie	B.Dreyer	

History Society Committee.

	<u>1974</u>	<u>1975</u>
Chairman	M.Morkel	R.Plowes
Hon. Secretary	I.Gwyther	T.Carroll
Hon. Treasurer	R.Allen	P.Nicholas
Research Co-ordinator	R.Plowes	J.Harris
Editor of Zuro	S.Gilmour	H.Ball
U.G.H.S. Representative	D.Hunt	F.West

.....

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY, 4th MARCH, 1975.

TRIBAL CUSTOM AND ORGANISATION.

Mr. N.A.Hunt.

There are 5½ million African people in Rhodesia, most of whom are Shona. What follows consists of generalisations from which there may be many minor variations in different localities.

Tribal Society.

- (a) The basis of tribal society is something unknown to our society - the extended family. This is an extensive system of relationships in which uncles are fathers, aunts are mothers, cousins are sisters or brothers. The families live in a kraal (musha) close to their relatives and are ruled over by the senior male (samusha) who acts as 'baba' to the unit, regulating all family disputes. He is responsible to the -
- (b) headman (sadunhu) who controls a number of kraals. He is recognised by government, is paid a subsidy and wears a badge. On average each chief has three to four headmen.
- (c) The chief owns the land on behalf of the tribal spirit and has the power to allocate it to headmen who in turn allocate it to family heads. It must be emphasised that land belongs to the tribe in the person of the chief: he can give the right to cultivate it but it can never be alienated.

The term 'chief' implies an autocrat or dictator; in fact he acts only in consultation with his 'dare' of tribal elders.

Marriage.

The system of 'lobola' would appear to one of paying for a wife - a straight purchase-and-sale transaction. In fact it is a complicated system originating probably among small groups living in a hostile environment wherein it was necessary to maintain the strength of the tribe - a woman, as a potential mother of children, represented strength (of numbers;) when she is lost to a hostile tribe through marriage the recipients must provide lobola (usually cattle) as compensation which in turn can be used to acquire a bride for a local tribesman thereby maintaining the strength of the tribe.

Marriage is by family negotiation and this system provides a stable society which modern African women are in favour of retaining.

Polygamy too has its advantages. Every woman has the right to be married and to have children; thus the childless spinster does not exist in tribal society. Wives will often encourage their husbands to marry again so that additional wives may help to lighten the work-load.

Totem System (mutupo/isibongo.)

This is not peculiar to Africa but is evident in Australia, Indonesia and America. Each individual has a totem - normally a bird, insect, animal or part of the body - which is inherited from his father and which he may not eat.

It serves as a tribal identification (eg. in greeting it is the first question asked of another) and is used in the regulation of marriage in that one may not marry someone of the same totem, thus preventing inter-breeding. A similar totem furthermore implies a relative and therefore a duty to protect.

Religion.

The African does not have the same concept of God as we do: he accepts the creator of the universe (Mwari, or Umkulunkulu) but he is not a fatherly image and has no interest in matters concerning the tribe or individual.

The tribal spirit (mhondoro) is normally that of the founder of the tribe and the tribe are his children; eg. the mhondoro of the Karange is Mutota, the Monomotapa who established the Karanga in the north in the 15th.

Civilisation has made little difference to the importance of the mhondoro; he is propitiated by the chief and is consulted with regard to tribal matters such as crops, rain and cattle.

The family spirit (mudzimu) is that of one's fathers and must be well looked after. There is no mercy in African society - "the cow licks the cow that licks it". Thus any wrong doing or misfortune is blamed on a failure to placate the mudzimu; if after placation the misfortune should continue, the cause is obviously witchcraft and the nganga must be consulted.

In spite of this there is no difficulty for the African in accepting Christianity: Christ is another mudzimu and the African is prepared to listen to him as well even though they might not be a member of his tribe. Christ must be white as only the whites can love both the Shona and the Ndebele!

Every family has a tree at which it placates the mudzimu - normally a tree with poles around it. A chicken or goat is killed, beer is brewed and with everyone seated strictly in accordance with seniority the kraalhead (samusha) addresses the spirit, offering beer and meat. No doubt the result is an increase in personal confidence much as we feel after attending church on Sunday or receiving Holy Communion.

Witchcraft.

Throughout Africa there is no exception - all know of witchcraft and all are terrified of it. Education has had little effect. One is constantly surrounded by it and anyone can practice it against one. The implication is that there is no certainty in the African's world.

Research suggests that witchcraft has increased, not diminished, with civilisation. As one suffers under the demands of a superior society so does one seek the aid of the supernatural; thus witchcraft flourishes in the urban areas.

Conclusion.

The African, group-orientated as he is, finds it difficult to fit into our society with its emphasis on the individual. This control by the group has developed a dislike of friction and tension: peace must reign in the group. The judicial system therefore is devoted to arriving at not what is legally correct but at a consensus of what is popular thereby satisfying the majority of the group.

Rhodesia's predominant problem is how to wed these two societies together.

.....

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY, 25th MARCH, 1975.

EXPERIENCES IN A POW CAMP.

Mr. G.Harris.

One of a large family, Mr. Harris ran away to join the RAF and completed his basic training in Scotland and Wales - navigation, air gunnery and astro-navigation. Training aircraft included the Anson (the wings of which flapped visibly several inches) and the Fairy Battle which was heavy and under-powered and required too long a runway to be practicable. Later Mr. Harris' name was drawn from a hat to navigate the new 'wooden wonder' - the prototype of the Mosquito.

Included in his Operational Training Unit was "F for Freddie" Pickard, a flying genius but fanatic. For example, before an operational raid on an

unexpected target over France, Mr. Harris ate something that disagreed with him and was forced into bed. Pickard nevertheless attempted to force him to go until a superior officer intervened. Pickard won fame in a raid on a French prison by destroying the walls without wounding the prisoners, but returning to check on the damage he was shot down.

On his last training trip - dropped at an unknown point and forced to navigate back - Mr. Harris found a considerable crowd on the apron as the plane landed: war had been declared five minutes previously. He was posted to 44 Squadron Waddington (later 44 Squadron Rhodesia) to fly in the Handley Page Hampdens, nicknamed the 'flying coffins' and carrying up to a 1 000 lb. bomb. After his first tour of duty he navigated with Sprog pilots who were undergoing a five week crash course in twin-engined aircraft - this was as nerve-wracking as any duty in the Battle of Britain!

He was commended when, during the German occupation of Norway, he had to navigate to a ship in the Skattegat and drop a magnetic mine from between forty and fifty feet. The mission was successful - 3 000 soldiers on the ship were drowned. Less distinguished was a raid on the marshalling yards at Ham when, out of a stick of six bombs, two fell on occupied civilian flats with devastating effect.

The first P.O.W. was George Booth (P.O.W. No 1, King of the POW's) who was shot down on a training flight over the North Sea ten minutes after war had been declared.

On August 14th, six aircraft were sent in a sortie against Berlin. Although the flying time involved was $8\frac{1}{2}$ hours the range of the aircraft was only 8 hours; thus the crews expected to be picked up off the East Anglian coast by MTB's. The raid was accomplished (and a camera attached to the base of the aircraft checked that the pilots did not simply ditch their load over the North Sea and claim a successful sortie) and in an atmosphere of 'more flak than air' turned for home. Four of the aircraft were shot down, one was later to ditch in the sea, but Mr. Harris' plane was hit in the starboard tank by a lone anti-aircraft gun fifty miles west of Berlin. With petrol as short as it was this was disastrous and it was decided to jettison everything and make for Sweden. But early in the morning the wounded plane was surrounded by German fighters and there was no alternative but to belly-land in a corn-field in Holland. The plane was followed down by the fighters who, after several victory loops, flew away without firing any shots. The aircraft was set on fire by covering it with a parachute (Mr. Harris still has part of that parachute which he tore off to use as a handkerchief;) also burnt out was the black box and 45 acres of wheat!

Making their way to the nearest village they saw a squadron of Germans but were able to march right past, being mistaken for German airmen. They made their way to the Dutch doctor and were taken inside to be fitted for disguise; a cleaner however, on the steps of the Town Hall, reported their presence to the Mayor thinking they were Germans in need of help. Very soon they were arrested by a German platoon.

Lord Haw Haw (William Joyce) occasionally broadcast, for propoganda purposes, the names of the allied crews shot down. Mr. Harris' name was broadcast, thus informing his wife within 48 hours of his fate.

He was first sent to Dulag Luft where conditions were on a gentleman-to-gentleman basis, mainly as the most relaxed method of extracting information! When Mr. Harris refused to co-operate (he had nothing to tell anyway) he was put in the cooler (approximately 4' by 5') and subject to extremes of heat and cold after which the Germans gave him the information - they had it already!

He was moved by train-horseboxes (8 horses or 40 men) to Stulag Luft I. Meals consisted of swedes, black-bread and marge, and occasionally meat. Barbed wire is the most unpleasant memory and was the most popular means of suicide - a means often unhindered by other POW's if a diversion was required.

With so much time to think there were many crazy schemes and humorous escapades. At Christmas each hut (10 rooms, 20 per room) was given a barrel of beer. In winter this was left outside and the contents would separate, the water frozen on top and the alcohol underneath. Two men, getting out of the hut, took a mugful from the tap on the barrel and were knocked-out by what was virtually pure alcohol! Frozen stiff they were later brought inside and surfaced only the following day with a raging thirst; the water they then drank sent them into a hair-raising tipsy spell again!

Mr Harris made clocks out of jam tins and sold them to the Germans at 10 marks each. Many took the chance to educate themselves by teaching each other at 'Stulag University'; the only paper available was toilet paper and much of it was sent back to England, marked, and the candidates passed. Sport was popular but weighing only about eight stone everything was in slow motion.

Two men were able to manufacture frocks; the Germans were greatly surprised to see a POW officer strolling around with a woman on his arm! Others volunteered to repair radios and although they might know little about it were able to return with four radios - in pieces. These the experts in camp were able to put together and the news from London was received once per week. One such set remained with Mr. Harris throughout the war.

Another POW, facing reality, wrote to his fiancée and suggested that they terminate their engagement. The next post brought a letter in which she described how she had inherited £15 000; a sympathetic Camp Commandant listened to the story and enabled the POW to retrieve his letter from the post box and tear it up.

Currency was cigarettes (Mr. Harris put dandyion leaves and grass into his pipe,) soap and chocolates, the latter two particularly useful for bribing the Germans: in the Nazi programme of 'guns before butter' chocolates were discontinued in preference to increased armaments.

Out of camp one day on a wood party Mr. Harris managed to escape and remained out for five days; it was hopeless however and he virtually gave himself up. The overall result was a transfer to Stulag Luft III of 'Wooden Horse' fame. He went straight into the escape committee and helped to make air ducts out of tins for the tunnel. Two hundred yards of air ducts were so made, but Mr. Harris was moved out of the camp three days before the escape.

During the Battle of the Bulge Mr. Harris was in a camp in Silesia, Poland. They told the German officers of the situation in the west and persuaded them to allow them to take over the camp. Out foraging one day some POW's heard a military vehicle and immediately hid in the bush, but it was a British Jeep of the Royal Irish Hussars looking for German tanks. A tank battle later took place with the shells passing over the camp.

Lorries eventually arrived to take the POW's to an airfield and finally home - some six weeks before the war ended. When they did get back the locals thought they were infested with germs, and to their bitter disappointment they were held in a camp in England. Some though managed to get out unobserved at night and return before roll call next morning. Eventually after medical inspection - by a lady doctor who was the first woman they had seen for some considerable time - the men were free at last.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY, 8th April, 1975.

THE HUNYANI SURVEY.

Mrs. M. Izzett.

An archaeological survey has recently been carried out over the basin of the new Darwendale Dam in the valley of the Hunyani River by members of the Prehistory Society of Rhodesia of which Mrs. Izzett is President.

In May, 1970, members of the society visited the Lazy River farm of Mr. E. Nelson to collect Stone Age artifacts for Mr. P. Garlake. Mr. Nelson pointed out a rock painting of a group of giraffe which would be submerged when the new Darwendale Dam was built; it was this which prompted society members to make an archaeological survey of the area before it was inundated.

All the farmers of the area were notified, exercises in map reading were carried out and Dr. T.N. Huffman was appointed Director of the Survey.

In the field the group would walk in an extended line backwards and forwards across the area under examination, usually defined by roads, paths, and fences. Particular attention was paid to gullies and antbear holes as they provided a good indication of what lay below the surface. A group normally consisted of four or five people, working over weekends and only in the dry season after the summer crops had been reaped.

When a site was found its position was located on a 1:50 000 map and marked with the serial number of the site. Surface collections were made of any remains - Stone Age artifacts, Iron Age potsherds, slag, iron, hut daga, etc. - which were placed in paper bags and taken to the museum where they were cleaned and identified by Dr. Huffman. In all 27 farms were visited, 50 sites were recorded and two test trenches were dug.

The Stone Age artifacts were mainly Sangoan although a small number of Acheulian-type handaxes and cleavers were found. The Iron Age finds were more numerous than expected and of the 35 ceramic sites it was possible to identify eight as vilages - one Coronation, five Maxton and two Harare. Most of the sites were near permanent water but were well-drained and free from loose stones. Finds included slag, tuyeres, furnace daga, a crucible, some copper bangles as well as pottery representing Coronation, Maxton, Harare and Refugee periods. A few low stone-covered mounds were found in the sandveld area, the appearance of which suggests graves.

Mrs. Izzett showed some slides as well as some of the artifacts to conclude a most instructive and enjoyable evening.

.....

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY, 26TH JUNE, 1975

THE S.I.B. AND THE INVESTIGATION OF WAR CRIMES.

Mr. Hitschman.

From 1933 -45 Germany was ruled by the Nazis under Hitler. The word 'Nazi' is an abbreviation of National Socialist German Workers' Party (NDSAP in German). Hitler's right hand man, Herman Goering, was made Prussian Minister of the Interior and in order to bolster the German Police under his command, he formed the SA (Sturm Abteilung, or Assault Detachment) and SS (Schutzstaffel or Protection Squadron) with about 50 000 men. The SA were drawn mainly from the working classes and were an ill-disciplined mob useful for street fighting and thuggery; by contrast the SS, an elite formation staffed from the middle class, were disciplined and very loyal to the Fuhrer.

In 1934 the SA became an embaressment to Hitler. Their leader Rohm, a known homosexual, was too independent for the Fuhrer and in the 'Night of the Long Knives' he and about 400 associates of the SA were murdered.

This left the SS and the Army in full power and loyal to Hitler. The SS was virtually an army within the army and was charged with special tasks, supposedly concerning the security of the Third Reich but in effect carrying out Hitler's ambition to rid Europe of all elements he considered 'unworthy of life.' Under Heinrich Himmler the SS organised the murder of some 14 million beings - 6 million Jews, 5 million Russians, 2 million Poles, $\frac{1}{2}$ million gypsies and, although it is seldom mentioned, 200 000 non-Jewish Germans and Austrians. The latter were either mentally or physically handicapped unfortunates or so-called enemies of the Reich like Communists, Social Democrats, Liberals, editors, reporters and priests who spoke out too frequently: men of courage and conscience.

In carrying out these tasks the SS made the two initials of its name and the twin lightning symbol of its standard synonymous with inhumanity in a way that no other organisation before or since has been able to do. Towards the end of the war its senior members, under no illusion as to how civilised men would regard their actions when the reckoning came, made secret provisions to disappear to a new life, leaving the German people to carry the blame for the vanished culprits.

When the allies finally conquered Germany the bulk of the mass murderers had gone under cover within Germany, suitably protected by new identities, or were among the thousands of POW's in the many camps throughout Europe. They had changed not only their black and grey uniforms for ordinary Wehrmacht uniforms of low rank but had also obtained false army papers to pass the initial scrutiny of Allied POW camp officials.

Towards the end of the war Allied Command realised that something should be done to investigate the numerous war crimes committed by the Axis powers. In the British Army the Field Security Section (part of the Intelligence Corps) was dealing with matters such as gathering by any means information of strategic value. However as reports of war crimes increased so did it become obvious that the Field Security Branch was not staffed to deal with them. At this time the British also had the Corps of Military Police (the 'Red Caps') the elite of which was the Special Investigation Branch, consisting mainly of trained CID and Police men, all professionals. To them was given the task of dealing with crimes committed by army personnel and, later when in enemy territory, by civilians.

At this stage it is necessary to explain how I fit into this subject. I had come to Italy in early 1938 to study engineering, originating from Vienna. When Mussolini declared war in June, 1940, the Italian police arrested me, having been a Czechoslovakian citizen and therefore an enemy subject. I was put in Milan Central Prison for one month, some of the period in solitary confinement, after which I was sent to a concentration camp at a small place in Teramo. In this camp were about 120 men of various nationalities, but mainly Yugoslav, Poles, Czechs, a few Chinese and Russians, all of them civilians who had been resident in Italy prior to the declaration of war. I spent three years in various camps in this part of Italy, being shunted from one camp to another.

On 8th September Italy capitulated to the allies; on the west coast the 1st Army was advancing slowly and on the east coast was the famous 8th Army of Montgomery. The Italian government had been taken over by General Badoglio who had exiled Mussolini to a solitary mountain resort hotel in the Abruzzi Mts., a place called Gran Sasso d'Italia, from which he was rescued by a group of German paratroopers led by the famous Colonel Skorzeny; they had managed to land with three gliders on a small plateau in front of the hotel.

The Italian camp guards had not been given any specific orders regarding the dispersal of their prisoners. I and several others absconded individually during the hours of darkness shortly after roll call. As I was badly fitted out for a hike I 'borrowed' a pair of army boots and a 7,65 Beretta pistol from the Italian Guards' dormitory which was temporarily unattended. I had a certain

amount of difficulty crossing the nearby highway which runs along the Adriatic Coast: it was swarming with German convoys, mainly reinforcements moving south to counter the advance of the Allied invasion forces. Keeping away from the troops and the main roads I walked west towards the distant mountains some 50 miles away. As I spoke fluent Italian I posed as an Italian army deserter and so managed to scrounge food and a place to sleep in hay lofts. It was the peak of the grape season and I fed freely from the numerous vineyards in the area.

After some nine days I decided to stay with a friendly inn-keeper in a small village situated on a steep hill. There I remained for several months dodging the periodic German patrols until in January, 1944, a group of khaki-clad, flat steel helmeted British soldiers fired on the building, but the Germans inside escaped. I identified myself and was sent under escort to Coy. HQ in the rear. I was handed over to the Field Security Section and interrogated for several hours, receiving clearance after a few days. I made formal application to join the British army and was attached to the Field Security Branch, staying with this unit for about six months and undertaking missions in civilian clothes near and behind the front line, which was very flexible and consisted mainly of patrol activities as no motorised transport was able to get there. My main task was to overhear German and Italian conversations and note troop and artillery movements.

I contracted malaria in the mountains and, considered a risk, was transferred to the 63rd Section, S.I.B. After a further three years I was selected to be part of the newly formed S.I.B. War Crimes Section. All reports concerning war crimes committed in our area were channeled through the Section; they had to be investigated, evidence obtained, suspects traced and eventually a complete case presented to the Allied Military Government Courts. This meant travelling all over Italy, mostly by Jeep, with a blank authority to draw rations and petrol whenever needed.

In 1946 the General HQ, 8th Army, decided that war crimes should be dealt with by the Army Judge Advocate General; again a new War Crimes Section, South East Europe, was formed and I was transferred to it. To give some idea as to the procedures adopted I will describe an actual case that was reported to War Crimes on 4th May, 1947.

70 Italian civilians, it was reported, had been killed in a village called Bergiola by unknown German troops. I was assigned to the case and proceeded to the village, the population of which consisted mainly of farmers and marble workers, and was able to ascertain the following facts. On the early morning of 16th September, 1944, a German sentry on the road leading to Massa, checking the identity of all passengers, was shot dead, presumably by Italian partisans. Immediately the German SS Comander ordered a reprisal action against the village and at about 4.00 pm SS troops together with some Fascist Black Brigade soldiers approached the village in four vehicles. They searched and looted all the houses and at pistol point ordered all the women and children and some old men into the school building where they were told they would be safe as the village was to be set on fire.

About 30 of these people died when the building was raked with sub-machine gun fire and hand grenades, and later set alight with flame-throwers. At the same time some soldiers went into a building where 28 persons were living and threw a hand grenade through the window, killing eight people including children. The remainder escaped through a back door. Seven of these were hiding in a chicken stable when six German SS and two Black Shirts opened fire with sub-machine guns. Only Dina Dell'Amica, 27 years old, and her cousin of 14, survived. In consequence of wounds received Dina lost her right leg. The rest of the 70 civilians were killed in small groups in different houses where they had taken refuge. A few hours after the soldiers had left the partisans returned and buried the victims in a mass grave.

I obtained a statement from Dina Dell'Amico who stated emphatically that she remembered having seen the SS insignia on the collars of the German soldiers. The Mayor of Bergiola provided me with duplicate death certificates and photographs of the exhumed bodies. My next task was to identify the German commander who had ordered the reprisals. Turning to the nearest major town, Carrara, I found that various units had passed through but from town-passes issued by the German commanders I was able to confine the name to one - Obersturmfuehrer Fischer - who I later found had commanded the 2nd Coy Pioneer SS of the 16 SS Panzier Grenadier Division, which was commanded by General Simon.

The name Fischer is fairly common in German. I instructed the Italian police to find any female acquaintances Fischer might have made during his stay in Carrara. They came up with a name and an address and I was able to interview a 19 year old girl who, at first not very co-operative, eventually produced an address in Germany and told me that Fischer was a carpenter and married. Searching the girl's apartment I found a photo of her together with Fischer in uniform, taken by a local photographer. I contacted the photographer, showed him the picture, and after a lot of searching he found some more negatives of photos taken of the same man. I therefore had a good set of pictures of the wanted man which I sent immediately to my HQ with the request to all Allied POW camps in Europe to arrest Fischer and transfer him to our HQ in Padua. Further enquiries also revealed the identity of three Fascist Black Shirts who had participated in the killing; they were arrested and kept in prison to await trial.

In the meantime I had ordered the exhumation of the body of the German sentry. In my presence the coffin was opened and the remains searched for the identity tag. This consisted of an elliptical aluminium disc perforated in the middle; in the event of death the tag was broken in half - one is left with the body and the other is used for identification purposes. This particular tag gave the soldier's name and the inscription 2/SS PI.BTL.16 which means 2nd Pioneer Battalion, 16th SS Panzer Grenadier Division, the same unit to which Fischer belonged.

Scrutinising our 'Wanted Persons' index I found that Fischer was also involved in an atrocity committed in southern Italy at San Terenzo. After several weeks I was notified that he had been located in a POW camp in Germany in the American zone and was handed over to us. I interrogated him for lengthy periods and he admitted being stationed at Carrara but denied any responsibility for the killing. He did admit to having ordered the reprisal but did not participate in the action and therefore had no knowledge of what his troops did. He had reported the killing of his sentry to his General who had ordered the reprisal. All Fischer had done was to obey an order. This line of justification was the usual one taken by war criminals: hoping to be absolved of responsibility by blaming a senior officer.

SS General Simon was put on trial in Padua. His defense too was that he had done his duty - it was not up to him to question the rights or wrongs of his superiors. Miss Dina Dell'Amico was called in as a witness. She walked into the court room on crutches and gave her evidence in a composed manner. On the way out she had to pass the accused. She stopped for a minute, stared at him, leant forward and spat in his face. Simon did not flinch.

He was found guilty on all counts and was sentenced to death. After the prescribed period he was hung in Germany.

Fischer was also sentenced to 15 years imprisonment, later reduced to 10. By now he should be in his fifties; I wonder if he ever dreams of the dead Italians of Bergiola - 41 women and 29 men, 17 of them children.

.....

Mr. J. Bekker also addressed the Society. He compared the Rhodesian terrorist war with the Malayan Campaign and went on to describe the purposes of protected villages and life within them. He showed slides of some of these keeps. Regrettably we are unable to publish the minutes of that meeting.

TREES OF HISTORIC INTEREST IN MANICALAND.

1975 is the Year of the Tree. The following project was completed on behalf of Mr. Petheram and the Rhodesian Tree Society; those involved were Mr. Barnes, J.Carroll, T.Carroll, P.Coventry, J.Harris, M.Mason, L.Moore, P.Nicholas, R.Plowes, S.Rault.

Stone Pines. These stand near the farm office of Claremont Inyanga Orchards which was built on the site of the original Moodie homestead. Reputedly the seeds were brought up by the Moodie family from South Africa when they came on the Moodie Trek. According to the late Mrs. Manica Harmer (nee Moodie) John Moodie planted the seed on the site where he shot an elephant soon after his arrival at Claremont.

The Inyanga Oaks. In 1896 Rhodes visited Inyanga for the first time and was deeply impressed with the beauty and promise of the area, thereby purchasing 40 000 acres. He returned in 1897 and for health reasons remained a long time; whilst recovering he began to develop his ideas on stock-rearing and farming.

His early managers were J.Grimmer and J.Norris. It was during the latter's period as manager that J.C.Johnson is reputed to have brought up from the Cape, at Rhodes's instigation, the acorns from which were planted the oak trees which stand at the entrance to Rhodes Inyanga Hotel. Previous consignments of acorns are said to have failed.

Rhodes's Indaba Tree. This wild fig stands on Claremont Estate near the Farm Manager's house just off the tarmac road. There is evidence that chief Sakarombe used it as an indaba tree but, despite the name, no evidence that Rhodes used it as such. It is in good condition although it is now in the middle of a fir plantation.

Rhodes's Gums. Rhodes selected a site by the Moodie Falls on the Mororo River on which he intended to build a boys' school. He arranged for some gum trees to be planted and these have now spread to form a pleasant grove just above the falls.

Meikles' Eucalyptus. These Eucalyptus grandis growing on Inodzi Farm beyond Penhalonga Hill not only hold the Rhodesian record for the fastest growing trees but also the world record for the shortest time taken to reach 100 feet.

There are 246 trees growing on 0,44 hectares; the average height of all the trees is 70,1 metres although several are over 100m. Individual diameters are as much as 1,25 m. and the total volume is 1707m³ - that is, enough sawn timber to build 110 average three-bedroomed houses!

The trees are situated on a steep and deep slope above a permanently flowing stream. There is also a leaky furrow high on the bank which supplies not only the homestead but the trees with water, meaning that the trees have experienced ideal growing conditions throughout their lives.

Incidentally the trees and homestead were, for many years, featured on the Rhodesian £1 note.

The Penhalonga Oaks. The silver oaks (Grevillea robusta) that form an avenue in Penhalonga village are believed to have been planted at the turn of the century. Grevillea robusta was widely planted as an amenity tree but experience has shown that its branches are brittle and liable to be broken by the wind. A recent inspection of the trees by the Forestry Commission has shown that about half the trees are likely candidates for felling whilst many of the remainder could be helped by tree surgery.

The Indaba Tree, Penhalonga. Apparently Ficus Buddha, or Morton Bay Fig.

It stands on the present site of the Nurses Memorial. The late Sir. Ian Wilson had an interesting theory as to the origins of these trees, which are scattered throughout the Penhalonga valley. He noticed the frequency with which they occur at the opening of 'ancient' mines - their evergreen, dark green shiny leaf makes them very prominent in winter. He suggested that the Arab traders came inland in winter only (to avoid the rains and diseases of summer) and therefore needed some form of marker to return to the following winter. It was these trees which were used as markers.

Mrs. C.Cilliers puts forward the assertion that Mushanje or Mhobohobo trees are found in the Odzi area only where the old gold miners worked. The fruit apparently is very sustaining and it is possible that it was carried as a form of iron rations. Furthermore the tree closely resembles the Chinese Fruit Loquat.

The Indaba Tree at Penhalonga is reputed to have been used as such by Chief Mutasa. Certainly in 1890, before the arrival of the Pioneer Column, Mr. Campion (manager of the Bartissol Mine which is nearby) built his hut under its branches. It was here that the nurses Rose Blennerhassett, Lucy Sleeman and Beryl Welby first stayed after their walk from Beira in July, 1891. Incidentally the plaque at the site is not strictly correct in that the first hospital was opened in September 1891 not on that site but immediately across the valley on Fort Hill.

Furthermore the present tree is not the original. In 1948 a swarm of bees settled in the trunk and Africans, to get the honey, set fire to the tree. It was pruned and propped up and seemed to recover but in 1953 it was struck by lightning. In the same year an off-shoot was planted by Dr. W.Alexander and it is this which stands in good condition today.

The Umtali Settlers' Tree. This is situated outside the Magistrate's Court. No reason for the name can be found. A bronze plaque underneath the tree reads:

'His Royal Highness, Don Luiz Filipe, Duke of Braganza and Crown Prince of Portugal, planted this tree *Rauvolfia inebrians* on 12th August, 1907, to mark the occasion of his visit to Umtali.'

Don Filipe was carrying out a state tour of Portuguese and British territories in southern Africa. He arrived in Umtali by train and after inspecting the guard of honour composed of 130 men of the local unit of the Southern Rhodesian Volunteers and the travelling escort of police, the "Prince rode through the gaily decorated streets of Umtali to the courthouse where His Royal Highness planted a tree in front of the building." (Rhodesia Herald, 16th August, 1907). A banquet was held in the evening after which the party left by train for Macequece and Beira. Six months later, on February 1st, 1908, the prince and his father, King Carlos, were assassinated whilst riding in an open carriage in Lisbon. The prince was then aged twenty one.

Rauvolfia caffra (synonym *R.inebrians*) belongs to the family Apocynaceae (which also includes, among others, the oleander, frangipani, sabi star and dipladenia) and is widespread in Africa south of the equator in forests and wooded riverine fringes. The watery, bitter sap was once believed to be a suitable substitute for quinine (hence the name 'quinine tree') but this is now open to doubt. Parts of the tree are occasionally used in rural medicine.

This particular tree does not seem to be in very good condition. It is small (5m. in height as opposed to the normal 20) and one of the main branches has been cut off and the stump sealed with cement. Perhaps its condition is partly due to the fact that the tree is surrounded by the tar macadam of a car park which prevents moisture from reaching the roots.

Other trees within the municipal boundary. Planting records were not kept before 1953, so exact planting dates for early trees are unknown.

In 1897 the Umtali Park was established and many of the older trees in the Park could date from about this time. These would include a number of palms and a specimen of Rhodesian Mahogany (*Khaya nyasica*.)

The row of Mahogany trees near the Sports Club appear to be as old as the Park specimen. The mahoganys outside UGHS Beit Hall were planted ceremonially by a visiting diatory but exactly who that was has not been determined.

At the top of Allan Wilson Rd and at Oak Avenue are two fig trees protected by the municipality because of their large size and age. That in Oak Avenue stands in a vacant plot that was once owned by Mr. John Meikle who placed a piece of machinery under the tree; the roots threaded their way through the machinery which is still there intact.

Rhodes expressed a wish that Main Street be lined with flamboyants. Several still stand today although the roots damage the pavement and the trees are thus likely to come down soon.

At the municipal dam in Tigers Kloof are some very large jacarandas planted at about the time of the dam's construction. Nearby is Umtali's original nursery in which several large jacarandas stand.

Border Eucalypt. In about 1920 Mr. John Meikle planted a fine avenue of *Eucalyptus saligna* in the garden of Border Farm which belonged to the Soffe's at the head of the Revue Valley. Their estimated height today is about 180'.

12 Mile Tree. This stands directly opposite the 18 km. peg on the road south and was the site of the first night's outspan for wagons leaving Umtali on their way to Cashel, Melsetter or Chipinga. It is a Mobola Plum, or Muhatcha (*Parinari curatellifolium*) and appears to be almost dead - white ants have eaten away most of the bark from the lower trunk.

Mutiusinazita (or 'the tree with no name'.) This stands on the banks of the Nyarushanga River in the Buhera District but it appears to be only an isolated specimen of an indigenous species found elsewhere in Rhodesia, and has no detectable historical significance.

Crocodile Bark Tree. This tree *Diospyros philoensis* has an obony black centre and is found in the Sabi Valley and Melsetter areas. At the turn of the century 1 000 tons were exported to England for use as piano keys, violin string bridges and rulers.

Devuli Baobab. (*Adansonia digitata*.) This large hollow baobab stands on the banks of the Devuli River near the new Trekkers Bridge - the room inside presently provides accomodation for an elderly African. Scratched on the trunk are several well known names, including 'C.D.Bowker, 3.12.1897' and 'Lindsay Oliver', both of whom were early Native Commissioners.

Melsetter Eucalyptus. Not many of these now remain in the village but they were planted very early in the occupation of the area - they were two years old in 1896!

Hollow Tree, Melsetter. Rather vague sources suggest that a local tribe elect their chief by sending claimants into a hollow tree which contains bees; those who are stung are rejected. According to Mr. J. Young, a hollow tree in the area is likely to be a parasite fig except in the Biriwiri Valley when it would probably be a baobab. The idea of bees selecting a chief is rather fanciful although the lower Manica tribes were at one stage renowned for their interest in bees.

Haroni Gap. According to the Outward Bound School some Eucalypt stand in the Haroni Gap south of the Msapa River (map ref. VP 963202) and mark the site of an old Portuguese customs house on the trail from Villa Perry, into Rhodesia.

In the early part of the century this route was used by the Melsetter pioneers to bring up goods from the coast. Their size suggests that the surviving trees are old although they have at some time been damaged by fire. They are at present on the Mocambique side of the border and therefore difficult to visit.

The Big Tree, Chirinda Forest. This giant red mahogany (*Khaya nyasica*) is estimated to be over 2 000 years old. It is about 16m. in circumference at the base and 60m. tall, thus earning the title of the biggest indigenous tree in Rhodesia.

Chikore Lemons. These trees are reputed to be very old and associated with an early Portuguese station. Despite several approaches however to local and national sources, no confirmation has been forthcoming.

.....

We would like to thank the following for their assistance :

Mrs. C.Cilliers, Mrs. O.Soffe; Mrsrs. R.Annan, J.Ball, I.Bickersteth, W. Broadley, J.Crosthwaite-Eyre, J.Lambert, J.Latham, A.Pellatt, R.Petheram, D.Plowes, A.Young, J.Young; National Archives, National Botanical Gardens, National Herbarium, Outward Bound School, Umtali Publicity Association, the Umtali Post.

.....

THE MOVE TO NEW UMTALI.

J.Harris.

In 1890 the first signs of settlement were evident in the Penhalonga Valley but late in 1891 it was decided to move seven miles west to (Old) Umtali. (Refer Zuro No.5, 1972.) After only five years the town's situation was again under discussion. The determining factor, as Rhodes made clear, was the railway. Because the cost of taking the line over Christmas Pass would be some £42 000 it had been decided to continue along the valley and over the Nyamashiri Range to the Odzi River. On March 26th, 1896, Rhodes held a meeting with the residents of Old Umtali (he had just resigned as PM of the Cape after the fiasco of the Jameson Raid) and discussed the possible movement of the town with them. Either, he said, the town moved to the planned site of the railway or it remained where it was and built a branch line back from Odzi. The meeting agreed that the town would have to move.

At the same time Rhodes and the residents came to an agreement over the conditions under which the move would take place. A suitable site was to be found on the direct line to Odzi, probably somewhere near the top of 'Leslies'; the new town would be built on exactly the same lines as the old one, so that owners of stands in Old Umtali would have an exactly corresponding position in the new town; a valuation of all buildings in the old town would be made and the BSACo would pay that value to the owners provided it was reasonable; the BSACo undertook to erect suitable government buildings and a hospital and to provide money for a water supply should the latter prove to be necessary.

It was then left to a selection committee, consisting of Sir Charles Metcalf, Messrs Mansergh and Pickett representing the government, and A.W.Suter who was chairman, to choose a suitable site. Their final selection covered the farms Weirmouth, Devonshire, Waterfall, with parts of Mountain View, Quagga's Hoek, Birkley and Sable Valley. For health reasons the BSACo. chose Sable Valley, Birkley and Mountain View and paid out £5 000 to the owners. Landowners in Old Umtali applied to the Surveyor-General, J.M.Orpen, to survey the new site, which was done, and it was agreed that if residential stands were unfavourably situated the owners would be allowed to exchange them for unsold stands. People were not allowed to own new land and retain land at Old Umtali at the same time.

It was suggested in May, 1896, the the local Sanitary Board was not

representative enough and that the move to the new Umtali should be accompanied by a larger, more representative form of local government. The last meeting of the Sanitary Board in Old Umtali was held on August 11th, 1897.

Earlier in that same year building operations had started and people began to move to the new site. The whole town was literally pulled to pieces and any worthwhile item was carried over Christmas Pass and reassembled on the new site, the surveying and laying out of which had cost £1 800. For a while there were two Umtali's and the population of some 90 Europeans was equally divided between the two. Every day wagons loaded with wood and iron toiled up the old Pass road and gradually the new settlement took shape, the dominant materials being wattle and daub cottages with thatched roofs. There was a shortage of labour in the new area since the Africans were distrustful of the whites and vice-versa; the result was an influx of labour from Beira and the Zambezi which introduced 'jigger flea' to the town.

Compensation paid out by the BSACo amounted to over £300 000 and it was the spending of this money together with the approach of the railway (it arrived in February, 1898) which resulted in the boom and initial rapid development of Umtali. The work of moving and re-building the town was supervised by George Pauling, then Commissioner of Public Works in Umtali. He also had £3 000 with which to construct a dam to provide the town with water.

Rhodes' interest did not cease once the new town was established; he ordered that the road between Penhalonga and Umtali should be maintained by the government; he undertook the planting of flamboyant trees along Main Street and he saw to the laying out of the present park as well as giving the town a tract of land which, for many years, was used as a race course.

Since the BSACo. had paid compensation to landowners, the ownership of the old town passed into its hands. When asked what he was going to do with it, Rhodes replied "We will turn it into a mission." He met Bishop Hartzell in Cape Town and suggested that the Bishop visit Umtali, which he did, arriving on December 10th, 1897. On 12th, in a general dealer's store, he conducted Umtali's first Methodist service. Negotiations were started and an agreement was reached in London between the Bishop and Rhodes for the establishment of an industrial mission on the old site, the handing over to the Methodist Episcopal Church the remaining eight buildings and 1300 acres of land, as well as concessions in the new town for church and school purposes.

References. The Rhodesia Graphic.

Chronicles of a Contractor - G. Pauling.

This is Our Land - F. Clements.

Kingsley Fairbridge - by himself.

Municipal Jubilee Supplement of the Umtali Post, 1964.

The Umtali Post City Status Supplement.

Where Lions Once Roamed - C. Hulley.

Rhodesiana, No 9 - an article by Mrs. M. Cripps.

Map. For a map to show the relative positions of the three settlements, please turn forward to page 20.

.....

INTER-HOUSE HISTORY QUIZ, 1975.

This year the Davidge Shield for the Inter-House History Quiz was won for the first time by Crawford with 41½ points, from Hill (39½), Palmer (32½), the UGHS team (26½) and Livingston (23.)

The best individual performances came from Roberts (17½), Mary Armour (16½), Gwyther (14) and Morkel and Munro both of whom scored 12 points.

.....

Mesopotamia: The Cradle of Civilisation.

R. Papini.

Two great rivers, the Tigris and the Euphrates, rise in the Armenian mountains, span a vast plain and empty into the Persian Gulf. The seasonal flooding of the rivers forms fertile mud flats across a great expanse of land; this land has been given many names throughout history. Ancient writers called it Sumer; the Bible refers to it as the Plain of Shinar; agriculturally this crust of rich salt and loam is known as the Fertile Crescent and until recent times modern Iraq was called Mesopotamia, the cradle of the civilisation of man.

Four thousand five hundred years before the birth of Christ the Sumerians descended from the mountains of Elam to the swamy plain at the head of the Persian Gulf. What gave these wandering nomad hunters the initiative to begin the first seed of civilisation? The great dynasties of China and the splendour of India were as yet unborn and the Egyptian civilisation, though not far distant, was confined to peasants scattering wild grain in the sandy earth of the Nile Valley. Europe was a loose, revolving mass of warring barbarian tribes from which, in centuries to come, would spring the Greek and Roman Empires. However it was the hardy Sumerians who first put aside their weapons and took up ploughs and hoes. Within five hundred years they had learned to control the flooding of the Tigris and the Euphrates by building earth banks and cutting channels and ditches; irrigation was the basis of the growing civilisation, whose culture included the building of dwellings of sun-baked mud, growing wheat, barley, vegetables and dates, spinning and weaving cloth and shaping some of the first wheels.

With the development of trade with surrounding civilisations which had emerged - Elam, Assyria, India and Egypt - the relatively-primitive Sumerian settlements swelled into prosperous city-states. Each state was considered the property of a particular god who was represented on earth by a 'patesi', or high priest, and continual chariot warfare waged across the open mud flats between the theocratic cities of Ur, Erech, Umma, Eridu, Lagash, Nippur, Sippar and Akkad, a Semitic state in the north. However war did not hinder progress and a mature culture developed, characterised by urban life, metal-working, textile manufacture, monumental architecture and the first script in history - cuneiform. This was a combination of wedge-shaped pictograms scratched on clay tablets with reed pens (Latin: cuneus - wedge.) Until 1857 AD cuneiform remained untranslatable despite the simple vocabulary of approximately 300 words.

During the middle of the third millenium BC, Semitic tribes from the Arabian Peninsula who, finding Egyptian power in the west and Hittite power in the north an impassable barrier, had settled in northern Mesopotamia and adopted Sumerian culture, became powerful enough to threaten the independence of the city-states. In 2550 BC Sargon of Akkad swept right across Mesopotamia to the deltas of the two rivers, conquering the quarelling factions of the city-states and carving out an empire which stretched from the Persian Gulf to the Mediterranean Sea. Then began a line of Akkadian kings, the most renowned of which was Ur-Nammu, who built a night 'ziggurat' in honour of Nannar the Moon-God; this was a pyramid-like temple the core of which was a massive earth mound enclosed by sloping walls up which climbed stairways to the altar. In about 2500 BC however, the Akkadian power declined and was expelled and a new era of independence and prosperity began for the Sumerians: the Third Dynasty of Ur and greatness of Lagash under King Gudea.

Then came the second wave of Semitic invasion, the Amorites, who engulfed the Sumerian city-states forever. The first flower of civilisation had wilted and a new bud was taking its place. This was the era of the rise of Babylon, the great capital city of the Amorite empire built on the banks of the Euphrates in 1894 BC. Babylon was so positioned that it monopolised trade from the Black Sea to the east and Syria, Palestine and Egypt to the west,

and therefore the Babylonian Empire, built on the foundations of currency, cuneiform, arithmetic and chariot warfare, swallowed the whole of Mesopotamia, halted only in the north by the barriers of the Hittite territory. From 1792 to 1750 BC the Babylonians were ruled by a great king, Hammurabi, whose fame rests on his celebrated Code of Laws which was to serve as a model to many subsequent nations. The Code has 3 600 lines explaining 282 laws, beginning with this statement: "When Marduk commanded me to give justice to the people of the land and to let them have good governance, I set forth truth and justice throughout the land and prospered the people." It ends with sixteen lines of blessing for those who obey the laws and two hundred and eighty curses for the disobedient. Hammurabi's principle was 'an eye for an eye, a tooth for a tooth.'

After the death of Hammurabi, the Amorite Babylonian Empire began to decline, and in the 17th BC the Kassites, a race living on the borders of Persia, conquered the capital and occupied it; another flower had fallen from the stem of civilisation. The Kassites however did not destroy the civilisation of Babylon but maintained it despite repeated attacks from aggressive neighbours, particularly the Hittites who were questing for westward expansion from their Armenian Empire. However due to the Hittites' invaluable discovery of iron-forging, Kassite Babylon fell in 1595 BC and was occupied by yet another race. Then fatally the technique of smelting, bending and honing iron was discovered by a far more warlike people living around the Assur in the Tigris Valley: the Assyrians.

The Assyrians were a nation fond of cruelty and devastation but also eager to replace what they destroyed with their own excellent culture. In 689 BC King Sennacherib besieged Hittite Babylon after subduing the surrounding territory and finally stormed the city; he had it utterly destroyed so that even the mud dykes that controlled the Euphrates were broken down, the streets flooded and the place became a swamp. After his maniacal rampage however, Sennacherib reconstructed the old town of Nineveh on the River Tigris, creating a city far more splendid than Babylon. So an inferior civilisation died to make way for a more advanced. Nineveh was supplied by a piece of architectural genius - an aqueduct more than three hundred yards long and containing more than 500 000 tons of stone. He also introduced cotton growing to Mesopotamia plus countless other contributions to a more advanced civilisation. Another king, Assurbanipal, boasted: "For a distance of twenty five days' journey I devastated the land of Elam. The noise of the people, the tread of cattle and sheep, the glad shouts of rejoicing, I banished from its fields." Yet this brutal conqueror was greatly interested in the improvement of education and collected at Nineveh a library of 22 000 clay tablets written in cuneiform script. The man who ruled Elam described himself: "Marduk, master of the gods, granted me as a gift a receptive mind and ample powers of thought. Nabu, the universal scribe, made me a present of his wisdom. I have solved the laborious problems of division and multiplication, which were not clear." Assurbanipal was named 'King of the World'. The Assyrian empire lasted in splendour for 250 years, the result of the gradual build-up of civilisation to a peak. Unfortunately the Assyrians had made too many enemies among the fierce nomads who roamed the fringes of the vast empire. Finally, when a weak king was ruling, two tribes, the Medes and Chaldeans, attacked. Assur fell in 614 BC; Nineveh fell two years later. The Medes and Chaldeans wreaked havoc, sacking Nineveh, ruining the palaces and temples and walls. Sennacherib's efficient irrigation system was wrecked and farming in Mesopotamia returned to a Stone Age level. It appeared that all civilisation had collapsed after a climax developed over thousands of years.

However the Chaldeans restored the glory of Babylon from a mouldering, swampy ruin to a city more magnificent than Nineveh, or anything history had ever seen. During the rule of its greatest king, Nebuchadnezzar, it was encircled by two sixty-foot high walls spanning eight miles. A moat ringed it, three hundred feet wide. Inside were palaces and ziggurats and the famed

'Hanging Gardens of Babylon'; these gardens covered four acres in a series of terraces supported by arches and pillars overgrown by creepers to give the entire area the effect of hanging in mid-air. Machinery raised water from the river to the garden and some of the galleries were made into apartments for the king and queen.

While the second Babylonian Empire was thriving in Mesopotamia, a power greater than any other seen in history had risen in the west. In 547 BC it moved through Syria into Mesopotamia. The last Babylonian king was supposed to have been feasting when the Persian attack began. Babylon fell in October, 539 BC when Cyrus the Great entered the city greeted by cheering crowds waving date palms. The days of the independent Mesopotamian kingdoms were over.

Mesopotamia, the cradle of civilisation, had at last been occupied by a civilisation which it had not spawned. However the past Sumerian, Kassite, Semitic, Hittite, Amorite, Assyrian and Chaldean cultures probably largely influenced the Persian way of life which was to dominate the Land between Rivers for another two centuries.

.....

THE PHILOSOPHY OF HISTORY.

The following is the basis of a talk given by S.Gilmour to a Sixth Form Conference at the University of Rhodesia on Saturday, 13th September, 1975.

.....

The term 'philosophy of history' could be used to cover virtually any branch of history but I shall use it in the sense 'does history follow any comprehensive pattern?' Looking back through the ages, all the major events or disturbances have been accompanied by a revival in the desire for self-knowledge among men. For instance, the French Revolution and the First World War both produced a significant change in man's thought and his way of looking at life. Man has become pessimistic, optimistic, frightened and even, very occasionally, been in a state of euphoria; all these emotions have set in action physical actions which have resulted in a certain set of circumstances which have in turn produced a new emotion. To this extent all our actions are predetermined by what has gone before, but this would be to ignore the personality, the intuition and the originality of man which will always combine in different degrees with a set of fixed circumstances. The emphasis one places on this will depend on one's religious beliefs, for religion of some sort often seems to be the only constant feature of our history. This then is what constitutes the 'philosophy of history' - a mixture of invariable and variable factors whose ratio will determine the quality of our being and thought.

Having explained the term 'philosophy', we must consider exactly what is meant by history. Much glamour has recently been attached to the word 'truth', so I use this with reservation when I say that history is the search for truth, i.e. to ascertain exactly what happened. Unfortunately we are faced with this dilemma - can someone who has been brought up in a particular society write accurately about what happened in another? The historian must be able to express his ideas in writing, and what he actually writes will depend on his attitude to collected evidence and the aim he has in mind when writing about something. "Most history," wrote H.R. Williamson, "is mythology's wicked sister, propaganda." History can be written with a national bias (as the Nazis and Fascists did) or it can be used to stress certain moral or political values, as is the case in many of our older textbooks. "What an excellent thing history would be," wrote Tolstoy, "if only it were true." Today this conflict between fact and supposition has largely been resolved: a magnificent precedent is set by William Shifer's 'Rise and Fall of the Third Reich.' The book is, I think, the closest we have yet come to truth about any comprehensive series of events in modern history for it is taken almost entirely from official documents which have no room for speculation about motives: it is the 'truth' about Hitler. Once all our books reach this standard then our task of looking for meanings, for a pattern, in history, will be much easier.

A point which must be made clear is that since history is a study of man in his past, and since man is a social animal, it is a study of man in societies, all of which have had some sort of philosophy. Philosophy always generates from the people, but a new era has begun with the introduction of Soviet and Chinese Communism whereby a philosophy has been imposed upon the people from above. The extent to which this has been successful we are not yet able to tell; what is important is that with these regimes, 'natural' philosophy has ended, for it can be regulated to give any desirable meaning. One can recognise in George Orwell's "1984" this indiscriminate shaping of our past and present, for the history teachers' task in Russia has officially been defined as "to educate his pupils ideologically and politically, to arouse in their minds a feeling of Soviet patriotism and selfless devotion to the cause of the Communist Party and Communist construction. We can never be entirely free from indoctrination but at least we must recognise its existence. "Historians are dangerous people;" said Khrushchev, " they are capable of upsetting everything."

The 14th Arab philosopher, Ibn Khaldun, is of more value than Khrushchev in

his assertion that "the inner meaning of history involves speculation and an attempt to get at the truth, subtle explanations of the causes and origins of existing things. History is therefore firmly rooted in philosophy." If we view objectively the entire historical process, and systemise it as we see fit, we should be able to make an intelligent prediction as to its possible future course, for as Benedetto Croce admitted, history and philosophy are identical.

In 1958 the Transvaal Education Authority claimed that history did have a purpose - God's purpose. The traditional approach of men making history but God working through them to ensure his will is done is still, to some degree, acceptable, but within this framework have evolved two distinct methods of approach to history - the cyclical and linear. It is dangerous to bring theology into history because it may lead to finding a pattern simply because we believe it to be there. Christianity must be one of the means and not the end of our historical enquiry.

The idea of a cyclical, endlessly repetitive pattern in history originates from the Greeks, which is not surprising in view of their intellectual bias towards philosophy and psychology. A leading exponent of this idea; Thucydides, claimed history will always repeat itself because human nature remains the same; he could not possibly have foreseen the changes in society which have instilled different values in successive generations of man. This cyclical view re-emerges with the Renaissance and the Machiavellian idea of man's self interest, which is still applicable today. He classified four stages of historical repetition:

- (a) Monarchy turns into tyranny and from the resultant revolt an aristocratic government is established;
- (b) Rulers succumb to greed and ambition, and oligarchical tyranny results;
- (c) The people rise and form a Republican government;
- (d) This functions for a while then men lose sight of their common interests, resulting in chaos and anarchy; therefore men look once more to a monarch.

The emergence of totalitarian governments has upset this pattern, but even the modern historian Hal Fisher claims that "The fact of progress is not a law of nature. The thoughts of men flow into channels which lead to disaster and barbarism."

This outlook is, I think, too pessimistic, and was altered by Vico in the 18th when he introduced the idea of progress within the cycle, turning the circle into a spiral. Modern historians such as Spengler and Toynbee have further advanced the spiral and are worthy of closer consideration. The former argued in his "Decline of the West" that:

- (a) The Age of Caesars was dawning in the west, and the Caesar backed by the most powerful military machine would emerge as Lord of the West;
- (b) The Imperial Era is the last stage of decline;
- (c) All energies of man are directed towards fighting and preparing for war, therefore war is no longer an incident of history but its central pivot.

Spengler was in many ways a remarkable prophet of the methods of Nazism, but is more valuable for the emphasis which he placed on culture as opposed to intellect, which had formed the basis of earlier philosophers. Unlike the Positivists (followers of Comte) he related the cycle far more to biology. He defined culture as an organic form akin to a biological form which goes through the complete life cycle of youth growth, maturity and decay. As a separate entity each culture possess its own spirit and therefore cannot borrow creatively from another; each culture possess its own maths, science, architecture, etc. Spengler dated western civilisation by comparing it with seven other cultural units of history - Indian, Babylonian, Chinese, Egyptian, Arabic, Mexican and Classical.

However he is now in danger of being forgotten because his 'comparative

morphology' became too rigid and he had to twist certain facts. There is too much violent German patriotism in his writings and, difficult as it is to conceive of cultures as living organisms, it is more difficult to believe in their complete independence.

Toynbee's work, "A Study of History", is of greater value because of his self-professed humanist respect for free will. He is more rational and spent 23 years writing ten volumes of history on the 21 civilisations which he considered to have spanned the last 6 000 years. Toynbee is no pessimist - he senses no inevitable decline in civilisations; it is only inevitable in that decay cannot be stopped once it has set in. A justified criticism of his work is that he is too quick to apply his theories universally; he based his patterns on Graeco-Roman and Western civilisations and applied the patterns to the situations with which he was most familiar. Sir Isaiah Berlin refers to such practises as "those enjoyable games of patience which Professor Toynbee plays with the past and future of mankind - a plays with exhilarating skill and imagination."

His declared aim was to compare civilisations so as to discover the cause of their rise and fall and so discover the possibilities of our civilisation. Civilisations arise as a response to a challenge, and are therefore found in a variety of environments. They grow as a response to the human environment, and there is no limit to the number of successful responses that can be made, although the responses are the work of 'creative minorities' rather than of society as a whole. The nemesis of creativity is that those who have created in the past tend to idolise their achievements rather than offer constructive solutions to present problems, thus effectively blocking the movements of a new minority and hastening decay. Unwilling to commit our civilisation to the same pattern, Toynbee lays hope in the synthesis of all the old churches to provide a strong Christian background to prove us the exception to the rule. In this he is confusing the role of historian with that of prophet - he is in fact crusading for a return to God, to a universal religion.

The process of writing history is the reverse of actual events; we know the end and work back towards the origin. The inherent danger in works such as those of Toynbee and Spengler is that the author is both the subject and object of his historical knowledge. Whatever their claims to objectivity, they are victims of unconscious indoctrination; therefore the way to understanding their books is to understand the author first. E.H.Carr tells us to "study the historian first, then his history ... Before you study the historian study his social and historical environment." This is what makes history an art and not a science: the historian can understand his subject matter more deeply and can explain it more fully than any scientist could ever do.

Isaiah Berlin has pinpointed what I consider to be the greatest weakness of all the cyclical theories. His argument is that if man is so conscious of himself and so correct in his self-knowledge, then the logical conclusion of psychology and sociology is that they will develop laws which will enable us to predict every detail in the lives of human beings of the past, present or future. All the so-called cycles must, of necessity, embody this idea, at least in some part. Because it is so obviously impossible I am inclined to disagree with the predictability and similarity of cyclical theories on the ground that man is not, and I hope never will be, a predictable animal.

The second major belief in history is that of progress - that of working towards some goal. There is however a tendency to confuse progress with evolution, as E.H.Carr points out, "by confusing biological inheritance, which is the source of evolution, with social acquisition, which is the source of progress in history." The idea of progress, which implies an ethical judgement of value, is that life is getting better and will continue to do so until a particular goal is reached. It is essentially a product of the last two hundred years: Greeks and Romans had little sense of the past or future.

Christianity in the Middle Ages involved a goal which was subject to divine will and which could not be attained here on earth; it was only after the Renaissance that men once more began to believe in themselves. Once the Church relinquished its stranglehold over men's minds, progress became an entirely secular belief, although it has modified to include biblical teachings.

The Christian belief is that history is linear in that it has a definite beginning and a definite end, in which the eternal life is fulfilled for true believers. Much of this relies on the fact of original creation, and the growing tendency today to reconcile evolution with creation will result in many people seeing in the Christian theory a working philosophy of life. Faith tends to fluctuate according to the sense of optimism or pessimism prevailing; therefore after works such as Toynbee's which claim that we are in the last stages of decay, there has been an upsurge in the Christian belief.

The father of the linear theory was St. Augustine, author of 'The City of God' in 410. He attempted to explain how the rise and fall of Rome fitted into the universal scheme; he concluded that Rome's function was to allow for the creation of a universal church, and once this was done Rome could fall away because she had outlived her function. Studies such as these are not based so much on history as on applying the truth of theology, and until Bossuet in the 17th century history remained under the sway of theology.

History was emancipated in the 18th century with historians such as Gibbon and Voltaire. They were affected by philosophies of enlightenment and thus emerged as being profoundly anti-historical in outlook:

- (a) They remained unaware of the need for society to maintain a continuity with the past;
- (b) They argued that man could only progress via reason, and they identified the past with the enemies of reason - a 'triumph of barbarism' as Gibbon described it.

It was this anti-historical philosophy which underlay the French Revolution, and it was the very failure of this revolution which forced them to change their outlook. It was reasoned that they had forgotten that there is a need to maintain continuity with the past, and from this developed the liberals who refined the concept of progress to allow for the concept of historical development.

Hegel, a post-French Revolution philosopher, first expounded the belief that history progresses through a conciliation of opposites. For a full understanding of the historical process he refers to the dialectic qualities of logic:

- (a) An idea, or thesis, is stated.
- (b) It has certain inadequacies, therefore its opposite, or antithesis, is stated.
- (c) Out of this conflict the most valid points of each emerge as a synthesis.
- (d) The is turn becomes a thesis for a new argument.

This process is continually repeated until we arrive at the ultimate truth. Thus, for Hegel, history is a process of upheavals: the French Revolution for example represents a direct collision between a thesis and an antithesis. This dialectic process cannot go on forever - there is a final goal which is the realisation of the ultimate 'Idea'. For him this was true liberty, which he felt was approaching in his own time (1770 - 1831.) Hegel is still useful for teaching methodology and can be used to explain certain epochs and concepts in history.

The degree of emphasis we place on Hegel depends on our attitudes to free-will and chance in history. Synthesis implies that given a certain set of circumstances, a certain result is inevitable; therefore the results were determined by what had gone before. This may be correct over a short period

but in the long run the criticism of Sir L.B.Namier holds true: "The subject matter of history is events and they are as complex and diversified as the men who wrought them, those rational beings whose knowledge is seldom sufficient, whose ideas are but distantly related to reality and who are never moved by reason alone."

Karl Marx was more of a revolutionary than a philosopher of history, but his interpretation of history, by bringing out the importance of economic factors, has had a powerful influence on all subsequent historical writing. He adapted his ideas of the dialectic from Hegel but he placed his goal (the creation of a better society) in the future, and whereas Hegel had emphasised the role of ideas in historical change, he placed more ideas on material conditions: it is not ideas, he argued, but the production of the means to support life which provides the key to understanding history. Economic means are reflected both in the sub- and super-structure of society and therefore all social phenomena are a reflection of the prevailing methods of production and exchange.

Marx believed all history is a record of class struggle and 'economic determinism - the ideology of history is dictated' by the economic world, and an economic revolution will bring an accompanying revolution in the ideology of men. He does not devote specific chapters to history, but we can discern throughout his writings the course he believed history was taking:

- (a) the feudal system resulted in feudal society;
- (b) Trade Unions and industrial revolution resulted in a bourgeoisie class - the antithesis of the feudal class. After a social clash the synthesis would be capitalism;
- (c) The capitalist class clashes with the growing proletariat and the ideal classless society emerges.

Marxists claim that history is a science and that it has strict laws of development which can be used to foretell its future course; the end is inevitable but it is still necessary to act now in such a way as to make sure it does happen.

All the cyclical and linear theories include some form of moral judgement. The question is, are historians justified in passing judgement of events which happened in a totally different society? This is perhaps an insoluble question which also asks is it possible to condemn the deed without condemning the man?

The major Roman historians such as Livy, Tacitus and Plutarch all wrote with a view to moral guidance; medieval historians saw history as the working of God's will while 18th historians such as Gibbon, Hume and Voltaire believed that history was "philosophy teaching by example." The development of a scientific approach to history meant that moral judgement was withheld, but in the early 1900's the works of Froude, Carlyle, Motley and Lord Acton all displayed a dislike for the morally neutral school. More recent writers such as Toynbee and Sir Isaiah Berlin have upheld the duty of the historian to deliver moral verdicts. There is much to be said for the case that although history is a record of change, moral laws are absolute: murder is always murder and the historian cannot adopt a neutral pose for he is part of history himself.

The First World War was supposedly a war to end all wars, but the emergence of totalitarian regimes and the Second World War destroyed public confidence to such an extent that there has now been a definite swing towards the idea of progress although the final end is now in doubt. The development of nuclear weapons, germ warfare and environmental warfare, coupled with a ruthless exploitation of the world's natural resources, leaves us less certain that history is the working out of God's will. This partly explains a shift within the Church to accommodate less controversial and more socially acceptable doctrines which pin more faith on hope than on fear. If we do not believe

history is purely cyclical then we must accept that the cycles are definitely building up to something.

A valid point is, I think, that history teaches us nothing - we must learn from it. I lay more emphasis on the unpredictability of man as being a valid learning guide, for with man ultimately rests the responsibility for events. The philosophy of history is therefore the philosophy of man, and an understanding of history should lead us to an understanding of ourselves.

.....

VOLTAIRE - THE FOUNDER OF THE "AGE OF REASON."

D. Warwick.

"I may disagree with every word you say, but I will defend to the death your right to say it." So spoke Voltaire, but his lifelong struggle for freedom of thought can most perfectly be summed up by his constant admonition to his contemporaries - "Think for yourselves." He was the first modern in an age of bigotry and corruption.

Christened Francois Marie Arouet on 21st November, 1694, he lost his mother at the age of seven. Educated at a Jesuit school he took the name of Voltaire at the age of twenty one. When he made known to his father his intention of taking up a literary career, Papa Arouet was appalled and forced his son into a law office. After making a dismal failure of this Voltaire was disinherited but within ten years 'Monsieur Voltaire' was famous.

Voltaire is widely, but incorrectly, considered an atheist. He never condemned simple faith but ridiculed superstitious credulity, the debasing counterfeit of faith. "The man who says to me, 'Believe as I do or God will damn you,'" he warned, "will presently say to me 'Believe as I do or I will kill you.'"

The censors greatly assisted Voltair success. Most of his books and plays were banned because of their undertone of criticism, which in those times was 'immorality' of the highest order. The overall effect was to spread his works like wildfire similar to the pamphlets of underground organisations.

After being put in the Bastille twice, Voltaire went to England. Here he was intrigued by the freedom of the people, the operation of British justice and the strength and independence of parliament. He returned to France in 1729 and, taking advantage of a government miscalculation concerning some lottery tickets, he bought them all and became very rich.

Faults Voltaire had in plenty. He was selfish, quarrelsome and a master liar but he possessed the most important virtue - he saw each man as a free moral agent with his conscience as the judge of his actions. He hated cruelty and intolerance, was deeply concerned with the needs of the poor but most of all he detested the privileged position of the clergy which was ruthlessly used to exploit the peasants. Voltaire detested the pious facade behind which the clergy hid whilst they were in fact corrupt to the core.

The work of this great playwright, author and philosopher totals about ninety nine volumes of plays, poems and articles and 8 000 letters to famous people. Numbered amongst his many admirers were Catherine the Great of Russia, Christian VII of Denmark, Gustavus III of Sweden and Frederick the Great (then Crown Prince) of Prussia.

In 1749 Voltaire finally went to Frederick the Great's court at Potsdam, but, indignant at the Junkers' militarism and amused at the court's pretension, he antagonised his host and in 1755 had to flee to Geneva. Three years later he bought an estate at Ferney, four miles from Geneva but on French soil.

Almost every great man in Europe came to see him here. Victims of social, religious and political persecution flocked to his protection and he set many of them up on his estate in the business they were fitted for, including carpentry, dairying, weaving and pottery. Thus Voltaire soon had a village on his estate.

When in 1762 a young man was found hanged in Toulouse, rumour asserted that he had wanted to become a Catholic and that his father, a gentle and weak old man, had hanged his son. When the father, Jean Calas, had confessed nothing despite terrible torture, he was hanged. As Voltaire became more interested in the case he began to uncover some stunning facts about France's criminal law. The accused was denied a jury, a counsel and evidence in his favour, and the accusers gave secret testimony while the judges acted as prosecutors. Moreover criminal law was not written down but memorised by the legal profession and they 'interpreted' it as seemed best for securing a conviction.

For three years Voltaire fought and demanded that the case be reopened and reviewed. Finally, due to public arousal, the case was reviewed and Jean Calas was declared innocent. Immediately victims of similar injustices rushed to Voltaire and gradually he began to reform French law.

But Voltaire adored France and was possessed by an insatiable desire to see Paris before he died. Thus in February, 1788, he made the journey. Paris exploded in welcome. The National Academy opened its arms; his plays 'Zaire', 'Mergre' and 'Mohamet' were drowned in cannonades of applause.

Finally, at the age of eighty three, Voltaire came to his death-bed. His final words, which he had his secretary record, leave us his creed: "I die," he said, "adoring God, loving my friends, not hating my enemies and detesting superstition."

Refused burial by the Church, Voltaire's body was taken outside Paris for a decent burial. Finally however, when the Revolution was in full swing, his remains were brought back to Paris and laid in the Pantheon where a quarter of a million people pressed forward to pay homage to "The Founder of the Age of Reason."

.....

OTTO SKORZENY

P.Zorn.

During the Second World War one of Germany's best and most valuable commandos was Otto Skorzeny of the Schutzstaffel (SS.)

He first came to world renown with the daring rescue of Benito Mussolini in September, 1943. With the collapse of Fascism no-one knew just where in Italy Mussolini was being held captive. Captain Skorzeny - also known as 'Scarface' - of the Friedenthal (a special formation of the Waffen SS) was ordered 'not to fail Italy's greatest son in his hour of need.'

On September 12th, 12 gliders carrying a force of shock troops approached the Albergo-Rifugio where Mussolini was being held in an isolated hotel; Skorzeny probably discovered Mussolini's position from an intercepted code message. The only way Skorzeny could reach the hotel was to crash-land practically on the doorstep of the hotel. He smashed the radio and entered Mussolini's room without a shot being fired. "Duce!" he said, "the Fuhrer has sent me! You are free!" After a hair-raising take-off from the plateau in an overloaded Fiesler Storch, Mussolini went on to Austria and Germany in a Heinkel which was waiting at the Pratica Di Mare airfield in northern Italy.

In mid-1944 Skorzeny, now a major, was ordered to conduct 'Operation Panzerfaust' - the takeover of Hungary - and to deal with Admiral Horthy, the Regent of Hungary. Hungary was a vital satellite to Germany both economically

and militarily, so terms had to be made with her especially as the Russians were on the borders of Hungary. To achieve this, the Regent, who was influenced by the Soviets externally and by his son Nicholas internally, had to be ousted.

On October 15th, during the meeting to finalise the surrender pact, Skorzeny and his counterparts bundled Nicholas into a carpet and flew him off to Germany, a prisoner. A rook had been obtained for the loss of a few pawns. When Admiral Horthy declared over the radio the new allegiance to Russia, Germany was pleasantly surprised at the reluctance of the Hungarian soldiers to accept the news. Skorzeny now planned the very delicate operation of capturing Castle Hill, Horthy's fortress in the capital. With his usual brass and bluff, he marched to the Hill with tanks and troops. It looked like a perfectly legal march-past rather than a battle array. The sentries at the gate received stiff salutes from Skorzeny and the tank commanders, completely fooled by Skorzeny's insolence. The astonishing capture of Castle Hill, sometimes known as the battle of Budapest, cost exactly seven lives.

The Regent however was long gone and the pro-German Regent, Count Szalasi, was Prime Minister, and immediately cancelled the armistice proclamation. Three days later Horthy was located and escorted by Skorzeny to a 'very secure' Bavarian castle in a special train, and had no further influence in Hungary.

This brilliant operation let Hitler out of a tight corner. The million Germans on the Carpathian front fought on alongside the Hungarian army which continued to fight to the last day of the war.

Otto Skorzeny also played an important part in the Battle of the Bulge in the Ardennes in December, 1944. He was to train special units of German commandos dressed as allies to travel in captured vehicles; they would go on ahead of the main German force and seize bridges over the Meuse.

Skorzeny personally led this group through the tangle and confusion of the Ardennes; he was able to despatch three of his disguised commando teams one of which actually reached the bridge at Huy. Ammunition dumps and communications were extensively destroyed and the U.S. Army was forced to set up elaborate identity checks - some U.S. officers spent a few vital hours in custody while their identities were being checked.

In the last days of the battle of Vienna, Skorzeny, now a Colonel in the Waffen SS, played his last significant role of the war. In April, 1945, he appeared in Vienna on a special mission from Hitler, hanged three officers from the Floridsdorf Bridge and claimed that the situation in the city was "dismal"; no orders were being given and despondency and "other signs of disintegration" were widespread. Skorzeny was finally thrown out by a protesting General Rendulic.

Otto Skorzeny survived the war and was not booked as a war criminal by the Allies. He will always remain in the annals of Germany's top commandos and masters of deception. He lived the remainder of his life in Spain where he returned to what was previously his original career - engineering - and died a peaceful death in Madrid in July, 1975.

.....

When Bismarck was ambassador to St. Petersburg in 1860, he noticed an armed guard patrolling a tiny spot on the lawn of the palace. Czar Alexander could not explain the unusual duty and ordered an investigation. Three weeks later it emerged that Catherine the Great had personally written out an order that a guard be posted to see that a tiny flower struggling through the cold earth be encouraged and unharmed. As late as 1912 - 116 years after her death - a sentry still patrolled that spot; a memorial to a flower and a tribute to a remarkable woman.

.....

MANFRED VON RICHTHOFEN - THE RED BARON.

D.Wylie.

This is part of the project that won first prize in the middle section of the C.A.H.A. Essay Competition last year. Unfortunately it has not been possible to include the many appendices, illustrations, maps and diagrams which completed the project.

.....

On 21st April, 1918, Rittmeister Manfred Albrecht Freiherr von Richthofen was shot out of the element in which he had gained an unprecedented fame - the air. He was only twenty five years old. In the short space of some eighteen months he had become Germany's premier ace and the greatest hero she has ever had. He had become the epitome of Wagnerian honour and courage, the embodiment of Prussian tradition. He was credited with more enemy aircraft shot down than any other pilot of the First World War and achieved a fame which still glows today, fifty six years later.

But Richthofen was a complex character: his thirst for fame, his compulsion for hunting, his indifference to women, his strict adherence to Prussian military tradition; all combined to make him the cold killer he was, to make him the greatest ace in the history of air warfare, and to hide that same coldness behind a blazing shield of glory. It is this glory, this fame, combined with the aura of mystery that surrounds his death, which makes the 'Red Baron' such an interesting study.

Manfred was born to Albrecht and Kunigunde on May 2nd, 1882, with an elder sister, Ilse, and later two younger brothers, Lothar and Karl Bolko. At the Richthofen estate at Schweidnitz, Silesia, the young Manfred enjoyed a life of goat-cart rides and exploring with his sister. At the tender age of nine he discovered guns. Alexander von Schickfuss, his mother's brother, was a dedicated hunter and, after hearing many tales of his uncle's hunts in Norway and Africa, Richthofen decided he would like to become a hunter too. He asked for an air gun, was given one, and began by hunting squirrels. Then he shot three of his grandmother's ducks and proudly showed three trophy feathers to his parents. They thought he was confessing, but he wasn't - he was bragging. It was a sure indication of his attitude in later life - he was to hunt his victims in the air with the same care and dedication he was to stalk wild boars in Germany's forests, and was to acquire a thirst for fame that reflected itself in his victory cups.

In 1903, at the age of eleven, Richthofen was sent to Wahlstatt, a cadet school in Berlin. He immediately took a dislike to the spartanly way of life and the harsh discipline - it is interesting to note that he was later to follow and enforce the same strict discipline on pilots under his command. He decided to work just hard enough to avoid being expelled and vent his frustrations on athletics and gymnastics, even winning a prize for the latter. The monotony of school life drove him to such desperate acts as climbing the local church steeple, where he claimed to have seen his handkerchief, still tied in place, ten years later.

Richthofen left Wahlstatt at the age of seventeen, after six years of misery and frustration. He now spent his time hunting and developed the passion for it that was to feature so greatly in his future career. Stalking thrilled him and he considered it unfair if the bullet was not placed cleanly; this again was reflected in the careful placing of his shots during the air war. Strangely enough Richthofen did not like to eat meat.

He was then sent to Lichterfeld School which he found far more acceptable than Wahlstatt, and 1909 found him studying, like everybody else, Clausewitz's "On War". Richthofen made friends with Prince Frederick Karl, with whom he constantly competed. He left Lichterfeld at the end of 1910 and entered the Berlin Academy of War for a final polishing up. He disliked the Academy and

compared it to Wahlstatt, but with the end in sight worked harder than ever. It was at the Academy that he became engrossed in horse-jumping - later he was to enter in several races, breaking his collar bone twice in the process.

Once his formal education was over Richthofen enlisted in the First Uhlans Cavalry Regiment and considered it most dashing. A Baron by birth, he was vain and proud of himself beyond all bounds, and revelled in the title of lieutenant, having been awarded his epaulettes in the summer of 1912. He was very happy and he and his friends spent most of their time playing cards and training horses to jump. They were rudely interrupted on August 2nd, 1914, when war broke out.

Richthofen led his first patrol that night when he took a party of Uhlans from the garrison at Ostrowo into Poland and saw his first Russians at the town of Kielce. Twenty four hours later the first Uhlans were on their way to Belgium. Richthofen received his baptism of fire in an ambush a few days later, losing ten of his men. He had been hoping to end the day with an Iron Cross. He was disillusioned with the cavalry however; there was a distinct lack of dashing charges and an even more distinct abundance of monotonous reconnaissance probes. The death of a cousin added to the boredom to put Richthofen in a sombre mood indeed. By the end of September he realised that the cavalry was finished; the French and Germans were trenching-up around Verdun, and a three hundred mile line of trenches and barbed wire was being set up along the frontier. As if to confirm his belief, Richthofen was posted to the Signal Corps, with whom he crawled around the trenches with despatches and later telephone lines. Despised as a 'base hog' - one who lived in relative comfort behind the lines - Richthofen became bored to the point of depression and went off hunting.

Then came the Iron Cross (Third Class) in recognition of his cavalry and trench exploits. Since the medal was bestowed upon some 5 $\frac{1}{2}$ m. men up to 1918 it was hardly a great award, but it was better than nothing.

In 1915 he was posted to the Supply Corps; Richthofen exploded, rebelled and applied for a transfer to the Air Service, a move he had been contemplating for some weeks. The application was approved in May and Richthofen happily set out for No 7. Air Replacement Section at Cologne for observer training. In early June, 1915, Cavalry Lieutenant Manfred von Richthofen left mother earth for the first time and, after the first rush of fear, enjoyed it tremendously. It made him feel powerful - again perhaps an indication of his superior attitude in the air in later life. He worked hard and was the first of thirty to finish the course, and was sent to No. 6 Air Replacement Section at Grosseenheim for another two weeks training. Fifteen flying hours later he was awarded his observer's badge and was posted to the 69th Squadron on the eastern front under the control of the Austrian Army.

Richthofen's first pilot was a reckless, tubercular man by the name of Zeumer, with whom he shared his first air battle on September 1st, 1915 - a rifle fight against a Royal Flying Corps Farman biplane. The Englishman put a few bullets in Richthofen's clumsy Gotha bomber and flew home. Richthofen scored his first victory a few days later while flying in an Albatross two seater with Lieut. Osteroth when he machine-gunned another Farman which crashed into a crater. His elation was soon dampened when he learned that his victory could not be confirmed as the enemy had fallen behind his own lines. Richthofen was furious.

It was then that he began contemplating a transfer to single-seater fighters, and he was still thinking when a posting saw him boarding a train for Metz. In the dining car he met Oswald Boelcke. Boelcke was Germany's first great fighter ace, a shy man with a square face and boyish eyes, undoubtedly a brilliant pilot who was already a national hero. He was later killed with his score at forty. Richthofen's meeting with him on October 1st

VON RICHTHOFEN'S FIGHTERS...

▲ FOKKER D.III

ALBATROS D.V ▲

HALBERSTADT D.V ▲

▲ FOKKER D.VI

FOKKER DR.I ▶

inspired him to learn to fly. Ten days later Zeuner pronounced him fit to fly his first solo. Richthofen crashed. However his sheer enthusiasm persuaded the Air Service to allow him to try for his pilot's test two weeks later. Richthofen failed. He tried again. Again he failed. A few more tries satisfied his examiner however, and he elatedly set out for Doberitz, a large pilots' training school west of Berlin. He was required to pass three successive examinations entailing various manoeuvres and cross-country flights, all of which he successfully passed without crashing once. He was awarded his pilot's certificate on Christmas Day, 1915, and was posted to the 2nd Regular Squadron at Verdun.

Richthofen first flew two seaters, and fitted another gun in addition to that of the observer, over the wing. A few days later he scored his second kill - a French Nieuport over Fort Douaumont. Again confirmation was withheld; again the plane had fallen behind enemy lines.

The squadron's main job was bombing, which Richthofen enjoyed in spite of his wish to be a fighter pilot. The squadron was posted to the Russian front where "half savage tribes from Asia are much more startled when fired upon from above than educated Englishmen." Richthofen found it particularly amusing to "pepper the gentlemen down below" but was later to come to dread strafing and the 'wall of flak.'

Then Oswald Boelke appeared, looking for talent for a new fighter squadron he had been ordered to form (he was later to form some 33 squadrons, or 'Jagdstaffeln'.) He invited Boehme, an old hand, and Richthofen, much to the latter's delight. They naturally accepted and packed their bags for Logincourt, France. Boelke scored the first victory for his newly formed Jagdstaffel 2 (Jagd meaning 'hunting') which he had decided to lead himself. He immediately began drumming into his young pilots what was to become known as the 'Dicta of Boelcke' - a set of rules for air fighting drawn up by the great ace himself. Richthofen was to stick to these rules throughout his career and to teach them to many others.

Richthofen scored his first official victory on September 17th, 1916, an F.E.2 (which he mistook for a Vickers Gunbus) flown by Lieuts. L.B.Morris and T.Rees. Both men died, Morris on the way to hospital after their aircraft had crashed behind German lines. Richthofen was elated, and he immediately decided to have a silver cup made and engraved with "1 Vickers 2 17.9.16" signifying the first victory, the type of aircraft, the number of men in it and the date. He was to maintain this famous collection of silver cups until his sixtieth victory, when silver became unavailable and he had to abandon it. The collection was undoubtedly a measure of his high self esteem - even Boelcke said that he had "an undeservedly high opinion of himself."

Richthofen's second victory followed six days later, a Martinsyde, with his third on September 30th, a flamer, which rattled him a little. He wrote to his mother to that effect, describing his heart as "beating a little more quickly." This is perhaps indicative of a period later on in his life when, after some ten victims in a row had gone down in flames, he developed a dread of going the same way.

Richthofen began souvenir hunting in earnest, obtaining parts of his victories whenever possible. He also fostered an ambition that was to become an obsession; that of winning the Pour le Merite, Germany's highest award. This was awarded to a pilot once he had scored eight victories - Richthofen was on the verge of winning it when the requirement was changed to sixteen. He was furious.

On October 28th Oswald Boelcke was killed when his plane crashed after a collision with Boehm's Albatross, not far from the airfield. His funeral was held at Cambrai Cathedral on November 3rd - Richthofen could not resist shooting down his seventh victim on his way there. Boelcke's funeral "night

...AND HIS VICTIMS

FARNBOROUGH B.E.2c

AIRCO D.H.2

R.E. 8

F.E. 2

SPAD VII

NIEUPOINT 17

BRISTOL F2A

SOPWITH CAMEL

S.E. 5

SOPWITH PUP

have been for a reigning prince", Richthofen told his mother - the great ace's death was a national tragedy and even members of the R.F.C. dropped wreaths on the airfield at Lagincourt in recognition of his bravery and chivalry. His body was buried in Berlin.

Command of Jasta 2, now called Jagdstaffel Boelcke, passed to a Lieut. Kimmair, who fell before the month was out, to be replaced by Capt. Walz. Richthofen's eighth victory brought the awards of the Order of the House of Hohenzollern and the Grand Duke's Medal; his tenth he commemorated with an extra large cup; his eleventh was probably the most famous - an almost surgical kill in which he shot down Boelcke's allied counterpart, Major Laneo Hawker, on November 23rd. Richthofen considered it a fitting revenge for Boelcke's death.

Christmas 1916 saw Richthofen's decision to fly an all-red aeroplane. Again it is a measure of his vanity; he wanted friend and foe to know that HE was there, and it is surprising that he was not reprimanded for violating the official colour scheme of drab olive-green overall. His decision led all pilots of his squadron to paint some part of their aircraft red, which made recognition easy.

On January 4th, 1917, Richthofen shot down his seventeenth victim, a Sopwith Pup flown by Flight Lieut. A.S.Todd. A week later he was given command of Jasta 11 at Douai, and on the 16th he was awarded the coveted Pour le Merite. On that day he became a national hero - and Germany's highest-scoring surviving ace. He scored his twentieth victory on February 14th, his twenty first the same day and his twenty third two weeks later. This was the start of the most productive time of his career, the R.F.C.'s 'Bloody April'. That month Richthofen scored twenty one victories. He also learnt what it was like to be shot down when, on March 9th, he was shot up by a D.H.2 and made a bumpy forced landing near Henin Lietaud.

His brother Lothar joined him in the middle of March and scored his first victory on his third operational patrol - he was later to score forty kills in seventy seven days of combat, and survive the war.

On April 29th, Richthofen scored four victories in a day, the last being his fiftieth. He was then ordered on leave and it is interesting to note that when he landed at Cologne and was surrounded by cheering crowds, he could not face the fame he had so studiously pursued and backed out hurriedly with a muttered apology. He tended to be embarrassed by situations not covered by the Prussians' code and disliked the many parties, dinners and congratulations and the endless glorification, and he sought refuge hunting in the forests. While on leave he also began his memoirs, eventually published in book form, and returned to Douai on June 14th.

Richthofen became close friends with Werner Voss and the two constantly competed for air victories, although Voss never came anywhere near Richthofen's score. Richthofen himself was taking an increasingly morbid view of the war, particularly after the death of an old comrade - in fact Richthofen never believed Germany could win the war. News of the death of Zeumer, his old pilot, did not raise his spirits.

On July 6th, Richthofen was shot down for the second time. Shot in the head by 2nd Lieut. A.E.Woodbridge in an F.E.2, he crashed well behind German lines and spent some time in hospital recovering, returning to the front on 25th July.

Then came the Fokker Dr.1 triplane, based on the British Sopwith Triplane. Richthofen flew one of the first two triplanes to arrive at the front - Voss flew the other - and immediately liked the little plane for its superb manoeuvrability. However he still leaned towards the Albatross D V for its superior speed.

In the meantime however, a new fighter group had been formed, known as Jagdgeschwader 1 (roughly equivalent to Wing) which consisted of Jastas 4, 6, 10 and 11. It was officially born on June 24th and Rittmeister Manfred von Richthofen took command the following day. The new wing was to prove so successful that another, J.G.2, comprising Jastas 12, 13, 15 and 19, was to be formed on August 17th. Richthofen's raised spirits at his new command and his promotion to Rittmeister (equivalent to Hauptmann, or Cavalry Captain, but abandoned after W.W.I.) were soon quashed when Kurt Wolff, an old comrade, was shot down and killed on September 17th, and when Voss was also killed on the 23rd after a brilliant but unequal fight against seven S.E.5's led by the British ace, James McCudden. Voss was shot by Rhys-Davis after having put bullets in all seven opponents. The two deaths weighed heavily on Richthofen and he became even more pensive and moody than usual.

On April 20th, Richthofen shot down two Sopwith Camels in three minutes; his score was becoming increasingly sprinkled with these fast fighters. That last Camel, flown by 2nd Lieut. D.G.Lewis, was his eightieth - and last - victory.

Manfred von Richthofen did not like having his photograph taken before a flight; it was supposed to be unlucky, and Boelcke had had his photo taken before his last flight. That fateful photo WAS snapped on the morning of April 21st - less than an hour later Richthofen was lying dead in the wreckage of his scarlet triplane. Richthofen's 'Circus' (so called because of the sometimes out-landishly decorated aircraft) had intercepted a flight of Camels of No. 209 Squadron led by Capt. Roy Brown over Sailly-de-Sec. Richthofen, flying Fokker Dr.I 425/17, broke aside to chase a Camel flown by 2nd Lieut. W.R.May, which was racing for home with jammed guns. Roy Brown broke off onto Richthofen's tail and opened fire as he got into range. At the same time Richthofen flew into a hail of fire from the ground directed by members of the Australian Field Artillery batteries. Brown saw Richthofen slump, then the triplane swerved and crashed just north of the Bray-Corbie road. The actual circumstances of his death have never been fully established. The kill was claimed by Brown and by several men on the ground, including Gunners Popkin, Weston, Franklin, Buie and Evans. Although Brown was officially credited with the victory most evidence points to the Australians, but it is unlikely that it will ever be established as to who exactly fired the fatal shot.

Richthofen was buried with full military honours at Bertangles on April 22nd, 1918. Seven years later his body was exhumed and reburied at the Invaliden Cemetery in Berlin. The tombstone, inscribed simply 'RICHTHOFEN', stands, pock-marked by bullets, by the present Berlin Wall.

Manfred von Richthofen's biography paints a glorious picture - he was undoubtedly Germany's greatest hero, praised, feted and publicised more than any other German before or since. But his character left much to be desired and a deeper look into his life reveals him as a man who was not all he was cracked up to be.

For example, was he the brilliant pilot he was claimed to be, as his eighty victories might testify? Apparently not. Rene Fonck, France's top scoring ace, was credited with seventy five kills, but may have achieved fifty more which could not be confirmed. Edward 'Mick' Manock, Britain's greatest ace, was frail and perpetually ill, and could barely see out of a severely astigmatic left eye, yet he achieved seventy three victories. Richthofen's own brother, Lothar, scored forty kills in seventy seven days of combat; Manfred took almost five times as long to score twice as many. Even Oswald Boelcke and Werner Voss were undoubtedly superior in flying skill. Richthofen's difficulty in obtaining his pilot's certificate also reflects this view.

It is therefore also significant that Richthofen never became involved in actual dogfights unless had had to; he preferred to hang around the edges and pounce on stragglers, or to stalk lone aircraft, sneaking up close under cover

of blind spots before opening fire. Unlike his brother, Lothar used daring aerobatics to gain his kills. The total contrast in character between the two brothers is an interesting point; where Manfred was cold and quiet, Lothar was gay and very much one of the boys; where Manfred seldom drank, Lothar was a tremendous drinker; where Manfred ignored women, Lothar spent plenty of time with the girls; where Manfred disciplined himself in all circumstances, Lothar was free and spirited. Their differences showed in battle too. Lothar's aerobatics revealed a love for flying that Manfred did not have; the latter, the mechanical killer, regarded his machine purely as a platform for his guns.

Manfred's 'hunting' tactics in the air revealed a native caution that was reflected in his hunting on the ground, but was no reflection on his courage; it took courage to continue to fight even after he believed the war was lost to Germany, as he had done from the very beginning. It was perhaps only that ever-present thirst for fame that drove him on, although after the award of the Pour le Merite he had achieved everything he had ever wanted, including the title "Ace of the Aces." One incident in his early life did reveal that streak of courage. When Manfred found out that their new house was reputed to be haunted by the ghost of a man who had hanged himself in the attic, he "determined to ... bash its supernatural brains in" and, aged twelve, slept with Lothar in the attic. When they were awakened by their mother and sister rolling chestnuts across the floor, Manfred prepared to strike the ghost with a large stick. His mother recalled that she and her daughter came very close to being clubbed "by a boy who did not show the fear he must have felt." Many describe a brave man not as he who has no fear, but as he who has and overcomes it. Manfred was one of those men.

Richthofen's vanity was something which showed through almost everything he did - his collection of silver cups, his self-centred letters to his mother, the painting of his aircraft red; all reveal this side of his character clearly. Incidentally he seldom wrote to his father, addressing the vast majority of his letters to his mother.

Richthofen's almost fanatical conformity with Prussian military tradition was another characteristic that underlay his actions - it was this strict adherence as much as anything which kept him fighting relentlessly. He never wandered from the beaten path of military discipline; a discipline which he had hated at school but had come to understand and enforce upon himself and his underlings both on the ground and in the air.

This stolid self-discipline, 'Prussianism' and patriotism to the air war led to another interesting aspect of his life - his indifference to women. Saying he had no time to indulge in such frivolities as taking girls out, or did not want to make a widow, he kept strictly away from women as a whole although he had a deep respect for them. He received hundred of scented letters and photographs from admiring girls but never answered them, and the many rumours of a romance were certainly not true. One of these was propounded while Richthofen was recovering from his head wound in St. Nicholas' hospital, where he was nursed by one Katie Otersdorf. Stories of a romance between them had no grounding in fact. About the same time, so the story went, he was receiving scented letters regularly from a mystery girl, all of which he answered. These letters have never been found and the rumour is equally untrue.

Throughout his lifetime Richthofen was immensely popular with the public. Apart from the hundreds of letters he received every day, he also also received Sanke postcards with his picture on for autographing, he was constantly stopped in the street to have his autograph or photograph taken, and he immensely enjoyed the interviews although he hated making speeches and kept them as short as possible. He could see his portrait in shop windows, films of himself in the cinema, hundreds of different photographs on the ubiquitous Sanke postcards. He revelled in the fame he had long pursued. The press described him as "shy", "quietly dignified" and "modest," They could not have been further wrong.

Ernst Udet, Germany's highest-scoring surviving ace, described Richthofen thus: "He was the simplest man I ever met. He was a Prussian through and through. A great soldier." Manfred von Richthofen was all that. Udet spoke of the great fighter with respect, but not with love as he would have spoken of Boelcke. It was an echo of the views of all the pilots who served under Richthofen; the deepest respect, but no love. They had loved Boelcke. As for his blood-red Fokker triplane, Richthofen did not invariably fly a red aircraft, as popular legend would have it, but sometimes flew others only partially finished in red.

Another fact which contradicts popular legend: Richthofen was never called the Red Baron by the Germans. Only some allied airmen called him the Jolly or Bloody Red Baron, the French calling him the Red Devil, as did some British infantrymen, others of whom called him the Red Falcon. As for the Germans, they invariably called him Der Rote Kampfflieger - the Red Battle Flier. However the possibly more dramatic Red Baron appellation, fostered by the Allies, has stuck, and spread to the screen, the record bars and the comic strips.

Richthofen's faults however, are no reflection on his importance. He was more valuable to the war effort both as an air fighter and as a moral example to the whole nation than any other German of the First World War. He built up a tradition that still survives today, in the form of Jagdgeschwader 'Richthofen' 71, flying Lockheed P-104 Starfighters. First commanded by Erich Hartmann, the Second World War's greatest ace with 352 victories, J.G.71 was preceded by J.G. 'Richthofen' 2 which, flying Messerschmitt Bf 109's, fostered such great German aces as Wick, Rudorffer and Barkhorn, with 56, 222 and 301 kills respectively. That was Manfred von Richthofen's heritage.

But Richthofen was far more important as a propaganda tool than as a fighter pilot, a fact he gradually came to realise and loathe. In mid-1917, during his leave, he wrote his memoirs. These first appeared as magazine instalments and late in 1917 as a paperback entitled "The Red Battle Flier." Some copies found their way to London where they were reprinted under the title "The Red Air Fighter" by 'The Aeroplane' in mid-1918. In his preface to the English edition C.G.Gray mentioned the book "as obviously touched up here and there for propagandistic purposes." Richthofen's family was distinctly less polite while Hans von der Osten claimed that Richthofen wrote nothing of the finished product. Meanwhile Sanke cards printed with various Richthofen photographs flooded Germany, films were made, even during the war, and the name Richthofen was plastered all over the newspapers and magazines, and portraits appeared by the dozen. Even his death did not stop the glory - more than 877 000 copies of his book were printed before 1937. The same year saw a spate of other books: "Richthofen, King of the Air," by Hermann Kohl; Karl Bodenschatz, Richthofen's last adjutant and a general in the Luftwaffe in W.W.2, wrote "Hunting in Flanders' Skies;" someone from the Luftwaffe's Military Science Section wrote "Captain Manfred von Richthofen: His Military Legacy," while Baroness von Richthofen contributed with "My War Diary." Herman Goering as head of the Luftwaffe wrote a foreword to almost every one of these books, writing of Richthofen in stirring tones which, although not entirely accurate, had the desired effect of enhancing Richthofen's figure in the eyes of the Germans and rekindling that fire which spurred the pilots in the second great air war to greater efforts.

The meaning of that propaganda has since been lost, but Richthofen has still spread to the bookshelves, the screens and the annals of song, and even to the comic strips, most recognisably in Schulz's 'Peanuts.'

Manfred von Richthofen's glory still blazes.

- Bibliography.
- | | |
|----------------------------------|------------------------------|
| Burrows ; Richthofen. | Rickenbacker; Autobiography |
| Caidin; ME 109. | Look & Learn, 1969-71. |
| Galland; The First and the Last. | Taylor; History of Aviation. |
| Green; Air Enthusiast. | 'Aeroplane Monthly'. |
| Mason; Air Facts and Feats. | Wonder Book of the R.A.F. |

GEORGES ERNST JEAN MARIE BOULANGER.

G.Grispos.

France's security has often been threatened by a young rising politician who has tried to secure power through dictatorship. Such a man was General Boulanger. Born in 1837, he entered the army in 1856, earning the reputation of being a 'smart soldier' and in 1880 he was made a Brigadier General with the help of duc d'Aumale. Two years later he became the Director of Infantry at the War Office and in 1884 Boulanger was appointed to command the army occupying Tunis. In later years however, he decided to turn to politics joining the Radical Party in January, 1886, and he soon rose to the position of War Minister. By this time Boulanger had become known as 'the only Republican General in France.'

As Boulanger introduced genuine reforms for the benefit of army officers and soldiers alike, he came to be accepted by the French masses as the man destined to give France its revenge for the disasters of 1870 and the recovery of Alsace-Lorraine. He also sought popularity in the most pronounced fashion, especially his dashing appearances at military reviews. No one since Gambetta had succeeded so well in capturing the hearts and imagination of the common people.

Soon members of the Senate began to taunt him for his ingratitude towards the duc d'Aumale but Boulanger denied he had ever used the words alleged. His letters containing them however, were published and the charge was proved. In December, 1886, he was retained by Rene Goblet at the War Office but he was becoming so inconveniently prominent that, in May, 1877, when Goblet resigned, most politicians were not sorry to see Boulanger go. The mobs however clamoured for their 'brave General' but Maurice Pouvier, who next formed a cabinet, declined to take him as a colleague and Boulanger was sent to Clermont Ferrand to command an army corps.

Soon a 'Boulangist Movement' was in full swing, with the Bonapartists attaching themselves to the General. The 'Compte de Paris' followers (the Compte was the Orleanist heir to the French throne) were encouraged by the Compte himself to support Boulanger, much to the dismay of those old fashioned Royalist who resented Boulanger's treatments of the duc d'Aumale.

In 1888 Boulanger was deprived of his command for twice coming to Paris without leave and finally on the recommendation of a Council of Enquiry (composed of five generals) his name was removed from the army lists. He was almost at once elected to the Chamber for the Nord, on a programme for the revision of the constitution. A popular hero survives many deficiencies and neither Boulanger's failure as an orator nor the humiliation of a discomfiting duel with Charles Thomas Floquet sufficed to check the enthusiasm of his followers.

During 1888 Boulanger's personality was the dominating feature of French politics and when he resigned his seat as a protest against the reaction of the Chamber to his revisionist proposals, constituencies vied with one another in selecting him as their representative. At last he was, in January, 1889, returned for Paris by an overwhelming majority. He had now become an open menace to the parliamentary republic and possibly at this time he might have executed a coup d'etat; but he did not do so and the favourable opportunity had passed. Eventually when Boulanger staged his coup d'etat it failed. The main reason for this was that he lost his nerve at the last moment and his incorrigible frivolity and laziness proved to be his downfall. As a result of his failure the government abolished the electoral device of 'scrutin de liste' and the system of multiple candidatures which had made his success possible. A prosecution against him had been quickly arranged by the government and within two months a warrant of arrest was issued.

On April 1st and to the astonishment of his friends (who still believed

that Boulanger would become dictator of France,) he fled from Paris before the arrest could be carried out, going first to Brussels and then to London. The political danger in France was over although Boulangist echoes continued for a short while. These echoes affected to some extent the voting polls of 1889 and 1890 but then disappeared completely.

Boulanger himself, in October, 1899, having been tried and convicted for high treason 'in absentia', decided to live in Jersey. He went first to Brussels however and on September 30th, 1891, as the result of pressure from both the French government and his devoted followers, he committed suicide. The legend of Boulanger had soon disappeared and his name quickly forgotten but his threat to the security and power of the Third French Republic was no less real for all that.

.....

THE ATOMIC BOMBING OF JAPAN.

M.Morkel.

By the spring of 1945 the ganglion of Government, Imperial Household, Army and Navy rulers who made Japan's national policy in the name of Emperor Hirohito, was struggling to end the disastrous war with a negotiated peace which hopefully would avoid Allied military occupation and, in all events, would preserve Japan's historic imperial system. Japan was clearly defeated: following failure to secure Russia's good offices for negotiations and the last hope for a conditional peace was the bitter proposal of the irrevocable Minister of War, General Korechika Anami, that Japan must fight to the end in defence of the home islands. Japan still had two million combat troops and 9 000 kamikaze (suicide) aircraft. These forces could be expected to wreak tremendous casualties upon American invaders, who in the end would be compelled to negotiate a peace.

American assessments of the situation were not vastly different to those of General Anami. Japan was defeated, besieged from the sea and was being pulverised by US Navy carrier aircraft and US Army B-29 bombers that were flying from bases in the Marianas. At a meeting in the White House of June 18th, 1945, US Army Chief-of-State, General George C. Marshall, urged that Japan should be invaded in order to end the war, and President Harry S. Truman gave the go-ahead for planned invasions on Kyushu on November 1st ('Operation Olympic') and five months later against Honshu ('Operation Coronet.'). While Marshall supported invasion, he was concerned about potential American casualties, estimating that 69 000 Americans would be killed or wounded in a 190 000 man operation against Kyushu. Japanese troops had amply demonstrated that they could and would fight desperately even when the outlook was hopeless.

One hope for enforcing a Japanese surrender which was discussed at the White House on June 18th, 1945, was a prediction of the highly secret US Army Manhattan Engineer District project that two Atomic bombs would be available for operational employment by the end of July. The first of these revolutionary weapons would be called 'Little Boy', a gun-assembly weapon with an explosive Uranium-235 core fissionable material that had been laboriously extracted at a giant Manhattan plant at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. Atomic scientists were confident that the gun principle would work, that an explosive charge would drive a plug of U-235 into the U-235 core, establishing a critical mass and an explosion of gigantic dimensions. The scientists however were less confident that the other type of bomb could be made to function. This was 'Fat Man' and it was an implosion weapon which used plutonium (Pu-239) bred in nuclear reactors at Hanford, Washington. The implosion weapon principle would require testing in mid-July at a proving ground near Alamogordo, New Mexico; if the principle worked, 'Fat Man' would be available at the end of the month.

The US Air Force had already provided everything required to drop the

atomic bombs when they were ready. The 509th Composite Group had been activated in December, 1944, under the command of Colonel Paul W. Tibbets, Jr., and included the 393rd Bombardment Squadron with the most advanced model long-range B-29 bombers - the only American aircraft being enough to carry the atomic weapons. The group had trained at Wendover, Utah, and in April 1945 had moved to North Field on Tinian Island in the Marianas. Both in training and in familiarisation flights in Japan, the 509th Group had been dropping orange painted 10 000 pound T.N.T. filled bombs (quite naturally called 'Pumpkin bombs') which were similar in ballistic characteristics to the 'Fat Man.' There was a derisive song being sung on Tinian to the effect that the 509th was going to win the war but no-one knew exactly how since only Colonel Tibbet and a few others in the group shared the atomic secret. A target committee on the Manhattan Project and Army Air Force representatives had nominated the cities of Kokura, Hiroshima, Neigata and Kyoto for the first atomic strikes but afterwards Nagasaki was substituted for Kyoto when Secretary of War Henry L. Stimson forbade an attack because of Kyoto's cultural antiquities.

American military leaders understood Japan's reluctance to surrender her ancient 'Tenno' or imperial system, and they also reasoned that the Emperor would be the only authority that could enforce a capitulation of Japan's military forces. The military leaders were therefore inclined to clarify the Allied unconditional surrender terms enough to permit Japan to retain her Emperor. This view was not accepted at the Allied Heads-of-State 'Terminal' conference at Potsdam. Instead the Potsdam Proclamation published on July 26th called for an unconditional surrender of all Japanese forces or else acceptance of "prompt and utter destruction." In the assessment of historian Robert Butow, the absence of mention of the Emperor in the proclamation was "an invaluable trump card" offered to the Japanese militarists and on July 28th Prime Minister Kantaro Suzuki announced that his government would 'mokusatsu' the proclamation - literally 'kill it with silence,' or more idiomatically 'treat it with silent contempt.' Suzuki favoured peace and may well have used the wrong word, but the response unleashed violent reactions.

Events moved swiftly and President Truman learned of the world's first nuclear detonation at Alamogordo on July 16th. The implosion principle, whereby a core of plutonium was wrapped with T.N.T. blocks which when detonated simultaneously squeezed the core into a critical mass, had worked and 'Fat Man' was practicable. In Washington, General Carl A. Spaatz, on his way to take command of the U.S. Army Strategic Air Forces in the Pacific, was told of the atomic strike plans and, after refusing to drop such bombs on oral direction, received written orders that the 509th Group would deliver its first 'special bomb' as soon after August 3rd as weather would permit a visual attack. The first bomb would be the reliable 'Little Boy.' The U.S. cruiser Indianapolis delivered most of the U-235 needed to arm it at Tinian on July 26th and headed on towards the Philippines (four days later it was sunk in mid-ocean by Japanese submarine torpedoes.) On August 2nd the 20th Air Force mimeographed top secret operation orders for Special Bombing Mission No. 13; the primary target was Hiroshima, with Kokura the second and Nagasaki the third. Since visual bombing was mandatory, an advance B-29 weather observer aircraft would scout and report on each target. The strike mission included an atomic laden B-29 and two observer B-29s.

Prediction of bad weather over southern Japan held off the attack until August 6th when at 0245 hours Colonel Tibbets lifted his B-29, named 'Enola Gay' after his mother, off the runway at North Field and was followed at two minute intervals by the observer planes. At take-off 'Enola Gay' grossed 65 tons in weight, eight tons over normal B-29 bombing weight, partly because 'Little Boy' weighted 9 000 pounds. Since a crash at take-off might have blown one end off Tinian Island, Captain William Parsons accompanied Tibbets as weaponeer and bomb commander, arming the bomb during the flight towards Japan.

Hiroshima Dies.

At 0715 hours on August 6th, 1945, the weather scout B-29 over Hiroshima

signalled that the target was on, thus sealing the fate of the city. Until now the city had escaped almost entirely air attack, and few people took seriously the appearance of a few high-flying planes; it was not even significant enough to call a defence alert. But those Japanese who watched the approaching planes (and who survived) noticed that the lead bombers, flying at 31 600 feet, suddenly separated in tight diving turns that carried them rapidly away from a point in space where something fell from the planes - 'Little Boy' from Enola Gay and parachuted instruments from the observation plane. Exactly seventeen seconds after 0815 hours, an instant of pure, blinding, utterly intense, bluish-white light, cut across the sky, followed by a searing heat, a thousand-fold crash of thunder and finally an earth-shaking blast that sent up a mushroom cloud of dust and debris to 50 000 feet.

As a military objective, Hiroshima was important as a port and the site of an army garrison. Located on seven finger deltaic islands where the mouth of the Ota river pushes out from the underside of Honshu in the Inland Sea, Hiroshima had been the point of embarkation for Japanese troops moving into China and to the South Seas. It was also the seat of the 2nd General Army, which was responsible for defence of the south-western section of the homeland. Hiroshima was Japan's seventh largest city.

'Little Boy' was aimed at a bridge in almost the centre of the built-up part of the city and it detonated at an altitude of just below 2 000 feet, almost precisely on its mark, with a force later calculated to be equivalent to 17 000 tons of T.N.T. In the blast and ensuing firestorm, approximately 4,7 sq. miles around where the bomb exploded was completely destroyed. Approximately two thirds of the buildings within ten square miles were destroyed or badly damaged. Very few people had taken shelter and the full extent of personal casualties will never be known. Japanese estimates were 61 000 while the U.S. Strategic Bombing Survey estimated 140 000 casualties (71 000 known dead and 68 000 injured.) Ironically for a strategic bombing attack most of Hiroshima's larger industrial factories were on the perimeter of the city and the factories and their workers who were at work who were at work escaped destruction. Only 26% of Hiroshima's total production plants were destroyed and these plants could readily have been kept in operation if the war had continued.

Nagasaki's Turn.

Whereas the execution of the 'Enola Gay' mission against Hiroshima was almost flawless the 509th Composite Group's second mission, flown on August 9th with the more efficient 'Fat Man' plutonium bomb, went much less smoothly. Again there were three planes in the striking force - an armed B-29 called 'Bock's Car' piloted by Major Charles W. Sweeney and two observer aircraft. The city of Neigata was ruled out as too distant for attack leaving Kokura as the primary target and Nagasaki as the alternative. The former was important because it was the location of a vast army arsenal on the northern tip of Kyushu while the latter had a fine harbour of some commercial importance and four large Mitsubishi war production industrial plants. Unlike Hiroshima's flat deltaic terrain, Nagasaki's topography was broken by hills and valleys which promised to reduce destruction. Both Kokura and Nagasaki were to be scouted in advance by weather B-29's. Prediction of weather over Kyushu dictated that the strike mission had to be flown on August 9th and since a storm was building up en route to Japan the three aircraft were scheduled to fly northward individually and rendezvous over Yakoskima Island.

There was considerable apprehension on Tinian as Major Sweeney launched 'Bock's Car' from North Field at 0349 hours on August 9th. Commander Frederick L. Ashworth was aboard as bomb commander and weaponer, but the 10 000 lb. 'Fat Man' had to be armed before take-off, greatly increasing the hazard of an atomic accident. Major Sweeney also discovered that 600 gallons of petrol could not be pumped from an auxilliary tank in his plane, and this substantially reduced his reserve fuel supply. Sweeney lost additional time and fuel circling

Yakushima Island awaiting one of the observer B-29's and after forty minutes he decided to go on without it. Apparently, during the delay, clouds covered over Kokura and after three runs over the city had failed to permit visual observation of the aiming point, the strike plane was headed for Nagasaki. It too was hidden by clouds and, in the emergency with fuel supplies steadily dwindling, Ashworth authorised a radar drop. At the last moment however a hole in the cloud permitted the bomb to be visually aimed. It dropped at 1101 hours but missed the assigned aiming point by about three miles thereby placing it over Nagasaki's industrial section rather than in its built-up commercial area. After the drop Major Sweeney headed to an emergency landing in Okinawa, arriving with only a few gallons of fuel in his tanks.

Only vague references to an 'incendiary' attack at Hiroshima had appeared in Japanese newspapers and the people of Nagasaki were little prepared for the atomic strike. Despite an air raid alert touched off by the weather B-29's, few people were in shelters. As at Hiroshima, 'Fat Man' was detonated in the air at an altitude of 1750 feet. The implosion principle of this bomb was much more efficient than that of the gun-type weapon and the force of 'Fat Man' was estimated at 20 000 tons of T.N.T. With the more powerful bomb, and surrounding hills concentrating the blast, the scale of destruction at Nagasaki was greater than at Hiroshima, but the area destroyed and personnel casualties were smaller because terrain afforded protection from radiant heat and ionizing radiations to about one fourth of the population. The area of greatest destruction was the narrow Urakami Valley while the intervening hills saved the central part of the city from destruction. (By comparison, in Hiroshima some 60% of the population was within 1,2 miles of the centre of the explosion, while in Nagasaki only 30% of the population was so situated.)

Official casualty figures include 24 000 killed, 2 000 missing and 23 345 injured while again the American estimate was much higher - 35 000 dead and about the same number injured. There was however no fire storm at Nagasaki and less public panic. Since several of the large factories were in the area of maximum destruction, damage to industry was quite heavy; excluding the dockyard area, 68% of the industrial productive area of the city was destroyed.

After a detailed investigation of Japan's struggle to end the war, the U.S. Strategic Bombing Survey concluded that in all probability prior to November 1st, 1945, Japan would have surrendered even if the atomic bombs had not been dropped, even if Russia had not entered the war, even if no invasion had been planned. On the other hand the atomic attack doubtless hastened the Soviet Union's belated declaration of war on Japan on August 8th and it certainly proved a powerful catalyst which enabled Japan's peace leaders to bring about a surrender over the continuing objections of War Minister Anami and the Army and Navy Chiefs-of-Staffs. After Hiroshima the Japanese militarists attempted alternatively to obscure the nature of the nuclear explosion and argued privately that the U.S. could not possibly possess enough radio-active material to permit a continuation of such attacks. The effect of these arguments failed with the Nagasaki strikes and in a hurriedly called Imperial Conference on the night of 9th August, Emperor Hirohito - the god-like figure who had never before been able to act without a consensus of his advisers - bluntly told the militarists that "to continue the war would mean nothing but the destruction of the whole nation," and that "the time has come when we must bear the unbearable." Thus by the early hours of August 10th cables were already on their way to Japan's diplomatic representatives in Berne and Stockholm announcing the nations acceptance of the Potsdam ultimatum with the sole proviso that the 'Tenno' system would be preserved.

A-Bombing - The After Effects.

In plans for the atomic strikes, Manhattan District scientists were knowledgeable about the potential effects of radiation emitted from nuclear explosions, although the exact effect of nuclear radiation on human tissue was, and continues to be, incompletely explored. Nuclear radiation consists of alpha and beta particles and gamma rays, the latter being of great signif-

icance because of their long range and high penetrating character. It was expected that the air bursts called for over the Japanese cities would limit casualties for the most part to non-radioactive injuries, namely those due to the force and heat of the unprecedented explosions. When the final results were known however, it was apparent from the experience that even without the effects of blast and fire the number of deaths among people within a radius of half a mile from the explosion would have been as great as the actual figure of people within a mile. The cause was radiation sickness or the "sickness of the original child bomb."

According to the Japanese, individuals very near the centre of the explosions but who escaped flash burns or secondary injuries, died rather quickly, the majority within a week. Autopsies showed the almost complete absence of white blood cells and the deterioration of bone marrow. Most radiation cases who were at greater distances from the explosion did not show severe symptoms for a week to a month after the bombs, when sudden fevers marked the often fatal onset of radiation sickness again with the same effects.

The degree of the fever and the chance of survival bore a direct relation to the degree of exposure to radiation. Sperm counts done at Hiroshima revealed low counts or complete aspermia for as long as three months afterward among males who were within 5 000 feet of the blast. Two months after the explosion Hiroshima's total incidence of miscarriages, abortions and premature births was 27% as compared with a normal rate of 6%.

At both Hiroshima and Nagasaki immediate deaths from radiation peaked in three to four weeks and practically ceased after seven to eight weeks. The atomic casualty lists were never closed since persons originally exposed have continued to die apparently though not conclusively before their time. Fifteen years after the explosion, for example, Japanese physicians began to find abnormal incidences of thyroid cancer in people who were young children at the time of the bomb, and there has been a higher incidence of eye cataracts and leukaemia among the bomb survivors. The social trauma of keloid burn scars borne by many men and women has immobilised survivors in varying degrees: many claim that they have been discriminated against because of their disfigurement. Although children conceived by exposed parents, have appeared quite normal, some scientists continue to fear that one or two generations born of atomic survivors must mature before the possibility of genetic mutations resulting from one day's exposure to gamma rays can be measured.

Conclusion.

In a retrospective look at the A-bomb strikes, Lieut.-General Leslie R. Graves, war-time director of the U.S. Army Manhattan District, has summed up the American belief about the matter. The atomic bombing of Hiroshima and Nagasaki ended World War II; there can be no doubt about that. While it brought death and destruction of a horrifying scale, it averted even greater losses - American, English and Japanese.

On the other side, the taped Japanese description of the bombing that may be heard in the Peace Memorial Museum in Hiroshima is more ambiguous, for here it is said that "When the Pacific War was finally about to end, at the stage where only a decisive battle on the mainland remained, the sudden disastrous event of Hiroshima was truly unfortunate to the people of Hiroshima, Japan and the whole world."

.....

"There is never so much lying done as before an election, during a war and after a hunt."

- Bismarck.

History Society Crossword: No 2.

Here is another History crossword - last year's was won by D. Warwick and his prize was a year's subscription to the Rhodesiana Society. Another worthwhile prize is offered this year; all entries must be submitted to Mr. Barnes before December 12th.

Across.

1. A battle in the Black Sea is open. (6)
4. Rhodes had a high one, and possibly Hitler's greatest asset. (5)
6. The Empire of Francis Joseph. (5-7)
8. St. Patrick's home in empire landforms. (7)
11. It is not, I hear; to blemish. (5)
12. A fitting conclusion to the Crimean War. (6 of 5)
15. politik - the art of the possible.
17. A bastion of Sebastopol. (5)
18. President of Tanzania. (7)
20. The Orleans monarch in record form. (2)
21. Count Alois von - appointed Austrian Foreign Minister in 1906. (10)
24. That body protecting the interests of weather bureaus. (3 - abbrev.)
25. Capital - in a Castro mercenary. (4)
26. 5 under a battle in the First World War. (5)

Down.

1. Latin's not the language for Uncle Jo. (6)
2. Count Karl von; the Russian Foreign Minister at Vienna. (10)
3. Equality of value with mother gives us an Italian Duchy. (5)
4. Even I thank you in Italy. (7)
5. ie. the United Arab Republic. (5)
7. Dr. Benjamin; PM of an independent Nigeria. (7)
9. Eton alters a diplomatic means of communication. (4)
10. A lekker fellow, this Israeli? (5)
13. A bridge too far. (6)
14. One strand wielded vigorously. (3)
16. Frederick the Great's capital. (6)
17. A straight and 12" monarch? (5)
19. Prime Minister Bevan to his friends? (5)
21. Dread mingled with reverence. (3)
22. Mussolini may well have used one in his brick-laying days. (3)
23. Definitely the past tense when the sofa is pulled away from Fashoda. (3)